

Building the EU Cancer and Health Genomics Platform

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Authors	
Name	Partner
Jaroslav Jirsa	PNED G.I.E. (Luxembourg National Data Service)

Contributors	
Name	Partner
Regina Becker	PNED G.I.E. (Luxembourg National Data Service)
Chloé Mayeur	Sciensano
Marlies Saelaert	Sciensano
Wannes Van Hoof	Sciensano

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Acronyms and Abbreviations

Charter	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
CTA	Controller for making data available
CTD	Controller for data disclosure to a specific user
CTI	Controller for initial data collection
CTU	Controller for the (re)use of the data
DGA	Data Governance Act
EDPB	European Data Protection Board
EDPS	European Data Protection Supervisor
EDIC	European Digital Infrastructure Consortium
EHDS	European Health Data Space
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortium
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IF	Incidental finding
IVDR	In Vitro Diagnostic Medical Devices Regulation
TFEU	Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union
SPE	Secure processing environment
WP29	Article 29 Working Party

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Summary

In 2020, 2.7 million people in the European Union were diagnosed with cancer, and another 1.3 million people lost their lives to it.¹ Nowadays, diagnosis and treatment of cancer has made already substantial advances thanks to the integration of next-generation sequencing (NGS) linked to precision clinical management of patients. Can.Heal aims to foster practical needs of developing the medical and public health cancer genomics platform and develop a trans-national collaboration enhancing the possibility to use the results in the project in other countries and to develop mutual trust for cross-border cooperation among EU countries. Can.Heal consortium aims to address the challenges through integration and alignment of genomics applications in medical clinical care and public health interventions to the benefit of cancer patients, their relatives and the population at large.

Work Package 12 (WP12) - Law, Ethics and Citizen Engagement is divided into two tasks:

- 1) WP12.1: Ethical and Legal Compliance Recommendations for Data Governance. Led by the Luxembourg National Data Service (LNDS) focusing on developing ethical and legal data governance for cancer genomics, including clearly defining the purpose(s) for which data will be processed, i.e. data sharing and secondary use for research, public policy, and clinical purposes.
- 2) WP12.2: Citizen and Patient Perspectives on Onco-Genomic Data Reuse. Led by the Cancer Center of Sciensano (the Belgian Scientific Institute of Public Health), this second task aims to formulate ethical recommendations for a trustworthy and democratic framework for genomic data reuse in oncology based on the perspectives of patients and citizens primarily, but also onco-genomic professionals of the Can.Heal consortium.

This deliverable is the result of the work produced in WP12.1. It has two main objectives. The first objective is to elucidate the European legal governance and policy frameworks, with emphasis on the potential barriers these frameworks pose to the sharing of genomic data with special focus on the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). GDPR establishes a comprehensive primary legal framework pertaining to processing of personal data and cannot be omitted from almost any activities related to genomic and health data. Its understanding is essential for data protection compliance. The second objective is to do a legal analysis of situations in which genomic data will be processed, which may include integrated screening and treatment, reporting of incidental findings to sequenced individuals and their families, as well as data sharing and secondary use for research, care of other patients and public policy purposes.

¹ European Commission. Europe's Beating Cancer Plan. Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament and the Council. Brussels : European Commission, 2021. https://health.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2022-02/eu_cancer-plan_en_0.pdf

The structure of the document is as follows. First chapter contains an overview of the key legal concepts of data protection terminology to help professionals using genomic data on a daily basis orient themselves in the elementary notions of the GDPR and understand how they interact with each other. This part of the document represents a necessary introduction to the second chapter which is an in-depth analysis of the GDPR with a special focus on the legal concept of legal basis, roles and purposes and their interrelatedness in the context of complex processing environments such as Can.Heal. It shows variety of legal and governance interoperability barriers, complicating cross-border genomic data sharing in Europe. The third part represents an analysis of the available and appropriate legal bases for secondary use of genomic data for envisaged purposes (scientific research, public policy development and incidental findings in clinical care).

Introduction

With a move towards routine genomic sequencing in healthcare and prevention contexts, there are important opportunities to re-use this data beyond the individual context, e.g., for research and public health, to develop clinical decision support tools, or to directly inform clinical interpretation for other patients. Realising these opportunities will require not only appropriate infrastructure but also appropriate data governance to ensure respect for data protection law and ethical principles. The European legislation, governance, and infrastructure for enabling the re-use of genomic and health data, such as the proposed EHDS Regulation, IVDR, and GDPR will also have important applications for cancer genomics. In data sharing the involvement of citizens and patients is also essential to successfully integrating genomics into clinical care, research projects, and public health policies in order to take account of their values, needs, and concerns to remain trustworthy and sustainable in the future.

Moreover, scientific progress accelerates this dynamic by improving the readability and usefulness of genomic data. Yet, the massive reuse of genomic data across Europe to fight against cancer and enhance personalised medicine, as pursued by the Can.Heal platform, raises numerous, complex legal challenges.

The methodology used in this document stands on reviewing data protection legislation (and case law), several other components of the data governance legislation (e.g., the EHDS Regulation proposal), professional and ethics guidelines, and associated literature in order to define key legal and ethical requirements that must be respected for cancer genomics. This deliverable provides answers/guidelines to the following genomic data governance questions:

- When do genetic or genomic data qualify as personal data under the GDPR?
- How and when does the GDPR apply to collaborative genomics research?
- Who is responsible for processing of genomic data and when?
- What are the legal grounds for secondary use of genomic data in healthcare and research?
- How can the GDPR's data subject rights and obligations be met in the context of genomic research and secondary use of genomic data?
- What requirements must be met for lawful sharing of genomic data within EU?

While the primary use of genomic (and health-related) data already raises various ethical and legal issues, it becomes even more challenging and complex in the context of secondary use, especially at the European scale. The reuse of sensitive, potentially identifiable data further heightens the risk of privacy breaches, which can impact the rights and interests of both data subjects and their families. Moreover, it is often difficult to specify the exact purposes, recipients, and risks of data use at the

time of initial consent, leading to questions about transparency and whether consent is sufficiently informed and specific. Even when consent is clear and well-understood, concerns remain about the effectiveness of oversight and enforcement mechanisms to ensure that data are used only for the purposes to which individuals have consented. Ultimately, transparent information is essential to enable individuals to make informed decisions about secondary use of genomic and health data, alongside strong governance frameworks to ensure responsible data processing. Additional concerns include the psychological impacts from the nature and volume of personal data being reused, and potential harm if data are misused or misinterpreted. Furthermore, there are additional legal challenges in handling research results and incidental findings that may affect participants and their families, compounded by limitations in healthcare systems' ability to provide appropriate follow-up care. Issues of vulnerability, such as the risk of discrimination based on cultural, ethnic, linguistic, or socio-economic factors, further complicate the legal and ethical landscape. In genetic and genomic research, specific concerns arise around therapeutic misconception, misunderstandings about the purpose of research compared to clinical trials, and confusion about the risk-benefit ratio. Ethical challenges are investigated in WP12.2 deliverable.

In a data-driven projects, researchers often need to access various data and sample collections from different institutions. However, securing access to these multiple collections can quickly turn into an administratively heavy and time-consuming task. Within two years of its inception, GDPR stalled at least 40 clinical trials for cancer, which exemplifies the risk in not sharing research data.² Additionally, the absence of incentives for sharing data, along with the costs and sustainability challenges of the related scientific, technical, and governance processes, pose significant obstacles to collaboration. This document's aim is to show legislative challenges in genomic data sharing for aforementioned purposes and present conclusions that are subsequently translated into actionable recommendations to the Can.Heal stakeholders.

² Eiss, R. Confusion over Europe's data-protection law is stalling scientific progress. *Nature* 584, 498–498 (2020).

Chapter 1: Overview of the Key Legal Concepts

In the genomic data processing chain, there are numerous personnel (healthcare providers, bioinformaticians, data analysts, scientists, laboratory personnel, technicians, etc.) who are directly or indirectly involved, usually as employees of a (controller or processor)³ in processing genomic data. In the field of health science, medical research and clinical trials, which share many features with policy development from the GDPR perspective, generally take place within an established framework of professional ethical standards. In this regard, knowledge of GDPR legal standards lags behind. Recommendations to develop consistent institutional guidelines for e.g. GDPR compliance among researchers with special focus on the grey zones between personal and non-personal data, or recommendations to clarify the exceptions subject to Article 89(1) of the GDPR with respect to permitted processing for statistical and scientific purposes, are one of the many suggestions to policy options from study how the GDPR changes the rules for scientific research.⁴ It is therefore necessary not only to create compliance recommendations for data governance but also explain elements and features of data governance to actors who are part of the data processing chain to be able to act in a compliant manner. The aim of Chapter 1 is to give an overview of the essential features and their interaction for Can.Heal stakeholders (and their employees) to be able to orient themselves in the essential European data protection legal framework, how it defines relevant data protection notions, and how genomic data sharing is influenced and limited. Even with enactment of the EHDS Regulation or other European or national laws, the GDPR stays the cornerstone of data protection legislation.

Genomic Data

Determining when genetic or genomic data are ‘personal data’ is challenging and can only be assessed in a context-specific framework. From the definition of personal data as “*any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person (‘data subject’); an identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier[...]*” the question at stake is: is it possible to identify a person from the data resulting from DNA examination technique? There are many techniques of DNA examination ranging from low resolution analysis of single base changes in a single section or small sections of DNA to detecting the presence of variants in many thousands of different short DNA sequences in parallel. The degree to which these technologies can be associated with an individual depends on the rarity of the detected structural change or variant, as well as the availability of supplementary information.⁵ When multiple variants are tested or technologies are combined, even low-resolution DNA analysis may become identifying. However, if the variants are common within a population, testing for multiple variants will provide relatively

³ See Chapter 1, subsection Roles.

⁴ Lenca, M., Scheibner, J., Ferretti, A., Gille, F., Amann, J., Sleight, J., Blasimme, A., & Vayena, E. (2019). How the General Data Protection Regulation changes the rules for scientific research. European Parliament. <https://doi.org/10.2861/17421>

⁵ Mitchell, C., Ordish, J., Johnson, E., Brigden, T. and Hall, A. The GDPR and genomic data. PHG Foundation; 2020 May. Available from: <https://www.phgfoundation.org/report/the-gdpr-and-genomic-data>.

limited information. For example, genetic markers such as single nucleotide polymorphisms or short tandem repeats could be considered personal data if they are sufficient to identify a person. Data from whole genome sequencing and whole exome sequencing represents a unique set of information that indirectly identifies a natural person, and therefore represents personal data. These considerations hold generally true for all common file formats of genomic data including binary alignment maps (BAM), FASTQ or variant call formats (VCFs).⁶

Apart from the DNA data that could be identifying a data subject per se, there could be other supplementary information related to the data subject. In Figure 1 there is clearly a set of genetic information in the frame 3 (containing both metadata and data). The combination of genetic information might not be sufficient to identify a person, however this genomic dataset is enriched by other additional information in frame 2 (also containing both metadata and data) which makes the likelihood of identifying a data subject particularly high. Furthermore, it is necessary to underline that the depicted dataset does not only contain genomic, but also health data, both belonging to the special category of personal data.

Genomic and health data (under the condition that it relates to an identified or identifiable natural person, i.e. not anonymised data) belong into the special category of personal data which is prohibited to process unless one of the conditions enumerated in the Article 9(2) of the GDPR applies. The general prohibition and existence of exemptions for processing special categories of special data should be read as rather strict interpretation of situations in which such data can be processed.

⁶ Evans, B. J., & Jarvik, G. P. (2018). Impact of HIPAA's minimum necessary standard on genomic data sharing. *Genetics in Medicine*, 20(5), 531-535. doi:10.1038/gim.2017.141

Figure 1. A cBioPortal Search Results

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Patient: P-0002788, Male, Colorectal Cancer (Colon Adenocarcinoma)
Samples: P-0002788

Attribute	Value
Age at Diagnosis	58
Age Groups	AO
Age Subgroups	AO
BMI	20.5
BMI categories	NW
Diabetes Mellitus History	0
First Line Treatment at Metastasis	adjuvant cape
First Symptoms at Diagnosis	"LLQ pain, straining defecation, change in stool caliber"
Hypertension History	0
Number of Samples Per Patient	1
Race Category	WHITE
Sex	Male
Smoker Status	Never

14 Mutations (partially visible)

Gene	Mutation
PIK3CA	
KRAS	
FBXW7	
PPP2R1A	
TP53	
SMAD4	R361H
APC	S1465Wfs*3
APC	R876*
SMARCA4	R1005*
FBXW7	R674Q

Pseudonymised vs Anonymous Data

The question of identification can be approached on three levels: data uniqueness, identification process, and practical identifiability. The first level addresses the required amount or type of genetic data to make the sample unique to an individual. The second is the procedural question of how identification can take place in practice. The third relates to the issue of how small possibilities or cumbersome processes should qualify as a relevant risk of identification.⁷

⁷ Rahnasto, J. Genetic data are not always personal—disaggregating the identifiability and sensitivity of genetic data, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, Volume 10, Issue 2, July-December 2023, lsad029, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsad029>

The GDPR defines ‘pseudonymisation’ as the processing of personal data in a way that it can no longer be linked to a specific individual without the use of additional information. This additional information must be kept separately and protected by technical and organisational measures. In other words, pseudonymous data can still lead to the identification of individuals, which is why it remains classified as personal data under the GDPR. **Pseudonymisation is not a method of anonymisation.** It merely reduces the linkability of a dataset with the original identity of a data subject and is accordingly a useful security measure. In Figure 1, frame 1, there is a unique identification number of a patient, which leads back to the source of study and to the patient himself which makes it pseudonymised dataset. **Pseudonymised personal data is still personal data** because it contains a unique identifier, or someone is possessing encryption key (if encrypted fully or partially) that leads to disclosing information on the individual. Pseudonymised data fulfils the legal definition of data relating to an identifiable natural person.

In contrast, anonymous data⁸ cannot be traced back to specific individuals. Once data is fully anonymised and individuals can no longer be identified, it no longer falls under the GDPR’s provisions/scope. In theory, genomic data could be considered as anonymous under two conditions: 1) the genomic data is not unique to an individual based on low resolution DNA analysis (e.g., only a handful of common genomic variants have been obtained using a targeted genotyping approach, such that the combination of the genomic variants is not unique in the relevant population) and 2) there is no unique identifier that could trace the data back to an individual. The latter condition will not be met if there is a necessity to reach back to a patient or a member of e.g., a research study. **Anonymisation of DNA data is not always possible.** Anonymisation is a process that should eliminate the risk of re-identification. However, depending on the context or the nature of the data, the re-identification risks cannot be sufficiently mitigated. This is particularly an example of whole genome sequencing or whole exome sequencing data which are, from its nature, unique and therefore always related to an identifiable natural person.

Roles

The GDPR mandates that the parties involved in processing chains contractually agree on their respective roles under the Regulation (key roles include controllers, joint controllers and processors, but also sub-processors and third parties), alongside their respective GDPR compliance obligations. The determination of the roles must take place in a manner that objectively reflects the nature and the extent of the parties’ involvement in data processing, which could be particularly challenging in network scenarios where multiple organisations are involved in processing data for different purposes.⁹ Roles determine who is responsible for protecting personal data and how data subjects may exercise their rights. **GDPR status hinges on control over processing, not control over**

⁸ There is a major difference between anonymising and anonymous data. Anonymising means rendering data anonymous. It is an processing activity regulated by the GDPR because at the beginning of the anonymisation procedure the data concerned was personal.

⁹ Becker, R., Thorogood, A., Bovenberg, J., Mitchell, C., and Hall, A. 2022. “Applying GDPR Roles and Responsibilities to Scientific Data Sharing.” *International Data Privacy Law* 12 (3): 207–19. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipac011>.

personal data. For example, you may define a research question (e.g. finding a reference allele frequency), then you submit a query in a SPE using its analysing software after which you receive the results. In such case you are the controller for the processing even without seeing any personal data, because it is you who determined the purpose and the means of the processing.

Controller and processor are two key roles.

Controller is a party with “decisive influence” over the purposes and means of processing (i.e., “the why and the how of processing”) deciding on:¹⁰

- the purpose(s) for which the data will be processed,
- which data to be collected and processed,
- the categories of individuals to whom the processed data will relate,
- whether the processed data will be disclosed and, if so, to whom, and
- the duration for which the personal data will be retained.

On the other hand, processors:

- are not processing personal data for their own purposes but on behalf of another party following their instructions,
- are monitored to comply with terms of the processing contract.

Purposes and means are key notions in defining roles. Regarding the determination of purposes, **only the controller has the authority to decide the purpose** for which data is processed. A processor is not permitted to pursue an independent purpose for processing. If a processor does so, it ceases to be considered a processor and instead should be regarded as a controller for that specific processing activity for which it determined the purpose.

With respect to determining the means of processing, processors acting on behalf of controllers may have some discretion in deciding how to process data to achieve the purpose set by the controller. As a result, both the controller and the processor may have a role in defining the means of processing. That is why the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) distinguishes between “essential” and “non-essential means.” Determination of the essential means is inherently part of controllership. By contrast, processors may determine other, “non-essential” means relating to processing, which concern “practical aspects of implementation, such as the choice for a particular type of hard- or software or the detailed security measures.”¹¹

¹⁰ European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 07/2020 on the Concepts of Controller and Processor in the GDPR. 07/2020. Para 30 https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2020/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and_en.

¹¹ ibid

Purpose of the Processing

Defining purposes of processing personal (genomic) data is a crucial component for the controller's overall GDPR compliance and **must be defined before any processing takes place**.¹² Its importance stems from the fact that it is inextricably connected with the majority of the GDPR principles (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, data minimisation, storage limitation etc.) and other essential notions, especially roles and corresponding responsibilities. Purposes and roles need to be clearly defined for orientation in complex data processing environments, where personal data are processed by multiple parties across longer processing chains, potentially for multiple, distinct purposes. A clearly specified purpose can help controllers determine what types of data they need to process in order to accomplish the purpose, alongside the required duration of processing.

This document's aim is not only to expound on application of the GDPR for the reader to be able to practically use its provisions but also create legal analysis of purposes. A key aspect is to clearly define the purpose(s) for which data will be processed, as well as analysing data sharing and secondary use for research, care of other patients ("clinical data sharing"), and public policies. "Research", "clinical data sharing" and "public policies" are not GDPR purposes (for they are foremost not specific enough) but merely distinguishing high level areas or categories of activities in which processing of personal data is required and secondary use is implied. "The purpose of the collection must be clearly and specifically identified: it must be detailed enough to determine what kind of processing is and is not included within the specified purpose, and to allow that compliance with the law can be assessed and data protection safeguards applied."¹³ For these reasons, a purpose that is vague or general, such as scientific research without more detail – usually does not meet the criteria of being specific. This requirement is especially visible in situations where controller relies on consent as a legal basis for processing. Consent to be given for specific purposes means a consent would not be valid unless the purpose is specified at the time of collection. As an example of a purpose could be "determination of a biomarker to predict disease X". Correctly defining the purpose for the processing is not always straightforward in a more complex processing chain and may necessitate multiple steps of refinement.¹⁴ Specifying purpose(s) is relevant for secondary use for it allows controller to assess whether further processing is taking place. Once the controller knows what the purpose was for the previous processing, the controller can assess whether the new processing is for the same purpose or constitutes further processing of personal data for another purpose. In this manner, the controller can demonstrate compliance with the purpose limitation principle. Every

¹² Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Adrian Thorogood, Edward S Dove, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Alexandra Ziaka, Olga Tzortzatou-Nanopoulou, Giovanni Comandè, Purpose definition as a crucial step for determining the legal basis under the GDPR: implications for scientific research, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, Volume 11, Issue 1, January-June 2024, lsae001, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsae001>

¹³ The European Data Protection Board, *Guidelines 2/2019 on the Processing of Personal Data under Article 6(1)(b) GDPR in the Context of the Provision of Online Services to Data Subjects (Version 2.0)*, Oct. 8, 2019.

¹⁴ Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Adrian Thorogood, Edward S Dove, Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Alexandra Ziaka, Olga Tzortzatou-Nanopoulou, Giovanni Comandè, Purpose definition as a crucial step for determining the legal basis under the GDPR: implications for scientific research, *Journal of Law and the Biosciences*, Volume 11, Issue 1, January-June 2024, lsae001, <https://doi.org/10.1093/jlb/lsae001>

controller needs to clearly justify that each processing of personal data is necessary to achieve the defined purpose. If such processing is not necessary to achieve the defined purpose, it is likely that further processing takes place. Such distinction is important where the processing is not based on the data subject's consent or a legislation and may therefore require a compatibility test. Genomic data processing usually consists of complex processing chains involving several actors, and therefore it is essential that controllers adopt a careful and differentiated approach to purpose specification, that is, by considering different phases of processing throughout the data lifecycle.

Legal Basis

Each processing must have a legal basis. "Processing" means **any operation** or set of operations which is performed on personal data or on sets of personal data, whether or not by automated means, such as collection, recording, organisation, structuring, storage, adaptation or alteration, retrieval, consultation, use, disclosure by transmission, dissemination or otherwise making available, alignment or combination, restriction, erasure or destruction. Once a purpose is disconnected from the legal basis (see below), it is necessary to either stop processing or have a new valid legal basis. Imagine an institution processing genomic data for purpose X based on consent. For purpose X, it is necessary to collect, store and analyse data. Collecting, storing and analysing data are three distinct processing activities, each one of them necessary to reach purpose X and covered by consent. If the institution wants to disclose the data to a third party, it needs to obtain a new consent, because this new processing activity is not covered by initial consent or find a different legal basis.

In identifying the legal (lawful) basis for the processing, the "starting point is to identify the purpose for the processing".¹⁵ Any data processing activity carried out using personal data must be based on one of the six conditions listed in Article 6(1) of the Regulation. These six conditions are referred to as legal bases. The party acting as the controller must choose the legal basis that best aligns with the nature of the processing. In cases involving special categories of data, such as health or genetic information, which is the case of data generated and reused in Can.Heal, processing must also comply with one of the 10 conditions outlined in Article 9(2) of the GDPR. The legal bases reflect both private law's feature of autonomy and discretion (what is not forbidden is permitted - consent, contract, legitimate interest) and public law's feature of legality and regulation of public bodies (what is not permitted is forbidden - legal obligation, vital interest, public interest). Purpose of the processing could be therefore expressed as a voluntary act (e.g. consent to process for specific purpose(s)) or as a mandate or possibility to process personal data for a purpose specified in a law (e.g. legal obligation of Danish healthcare organisations generating clinical-grade genomic data to report or transfer the data to the Danish National Genome Centre).¹⁶ In theory, the controller has significant discretion in selecting from the six legal bases for processing. However, in practice, the available options are often limited, with the choice being influenced by the specific nature of the processing operation, the

¹⁵ The European Data Protection Board, Guidelines 2/2019 on the Processing of Personal Data under Article 6(1)(b) GDPR in the Context of the Provision of Online Services to Data Subjects (Version 2.0), Oct. 8, 2019.

¹⁶ Kristina Laugesen and others, 'A Review of Major Danish Biobanks: Advantages and Possibilities of Health Research in Denmark' (2023) 15 *Clinical Epidemiology* 213.

national implementation of the GDPR in the controller's country, and other relevant constraints. Despite only six legal bases there are limitless numbers of sufficiently specific purposes for which genomic data could be processed which in combination with different legal regimes and requirements makes difficult to find common shared denominator for cross-border secondary use, especially when national implementations of the GDPR have already diverged dramatically in their interpretation of GDPR Articles 6(1) and 9(2).¹⁷

Secondary use and Further Processing

The GDPR focusses always on the fact that data are processed and the reasons why they are processed, building its definitions and framework around the processing operations and the purposes.¹⁸

- Data-focussed view, which concentrates on a whole data lifecycle from creation to deletion of a **data**, and
- Controller-focussed view, which reflects **who** is processing data and for what purposes. In this view, the data lifecycle starts when a controller collects personal data (directly from data subject or indirectly from other sources) and concludes once the purposes for which the controller collected the data are fulfilled.

For being GDPR compliant, the controller-focused view is essential. However, understanding the data-focused view is necessary for orientation in the data lifecycle and terms like secondary use, reuse, repurposing etc., which are used mostly in relation to the data itself rather than the user of the data.

Secondary use of data is a term that could acquire many forms and is used mainly to distinguish the existence of primary purpose/use/user etc. of the data from any other purpose/use/user etc. of the data. Primary and secondary use are binary and rather data-focussed view terms, where secondary use (or reuse, repurposing etc.) lacks a precise consensus definition and refers to any use of the data beyond the scope for which the data were initially collected or generated. GDPR, as mentioned earlier, focuses on one aspect of the data, which is who shall be responsible for the processing of it (the controller focused view).

Further processing is a GDPR concept having significant impact on the GDPR compliance. Although further processing is not explicitly defined, the principle of purpose limitation in the Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR states that personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes. Further processing

¹⁷ Roxanne Meilak Borg and Mireille Martine Caruana, 'Alternative Legal Bases for Processing Health Data for Scientific Research Purposes' (2024) 18 Masaryk University Journal of Law and Technology

¹⁸ Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It "Further Processing" Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?. *European Journal of Health Law*, 30(2), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

refers to “processing of personal data for purposes other than those for which the personal data were initially collected.”¹⁹ This has significant implications on any genomic data reuse because of the general requirement of collecting data for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes.²⁰ There are exemptions to the purpose limitation principle. Further processing purposes are deemed compatible with the original purpose when a controller:

- can rely on consent of the data subject,
- the processing is based on a Union or a Member State law,
- is further processing for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes (also requires a Union or a Member State law).

It is necessary to underline that further processing is always performed by a data controller that has already collected the data for another purpose (e.g., granting access to genomic database in which data has been collected for purpose X) , as opposed to a controller that is requesting access to the data to process them for its own (primary) purpose Y. Also, it is possible for data to be shared with multiple independent controllers without any further processing taking place. In the context of personal health data, this is most notably the case where the data are collected from individuals with an explicit primary purpose of making the data available for external parties.²¹

Additionally, other legal and regulatory limitations, such as those stemming from the discretion granted to EU Member States to impose further restrictions on the processing of health and genetic data, may potentially hinder the data controller's ability to carry out the intended further processing. (E.g., always requiring the patient’s consent for data reuse in another research project, and/or requiring an ethics approval for each reuse).

Data Subjects’ Rights

Data subject has rights stemming from his right to private life that need to be respected. The right to data protection and the right to private life are closely related, but they are not interchangeable. By protecting personal data, we also safeguard an individual. Data subjects’ rights refer to the group of rights that data protection law, in this case GDPR, grants to individuals. The GDPR contains an extended catalogue of subjective rights providing for appropriate ground for the data subjects to exercise them. However, it also contains clauses limiting the enforceability of such rights leaving substantial discretion to Member States, especially in the area of scientific research.

¹⁹ Recital 50 of the GDPR

²⁰ Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR

²¹ Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It “Further Processing” Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?. *European Journal of Health Law*, 30(2), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

In complex data processing scenarios, the initial controller typically bears the responsibility for assisting data subjects in exercising their rights in relation to other controllers. This support is essential during the secondary use of data. When a data subject submits a request to the initial controller to exercise their rights, the initial controller should inform all recipients of the personal data, including downstream controllers, about the data subject's information. This notification requirement applies unless doing so is "impossible or involves disproportionate effort." Downstream controllers may lack the ability to verify the identity of the data subject, which is particularly relevant in the Can.Heal context, where the data is robustly pseudonymised, and downstream controllers are unlikely to possess the necessary information to authenticate data subjects. As a result, it is likely that the involvement of the initial controller will be required to facilitate the exercise of all data subject rights.

Chapter 2: Data Protection View

The complexity of the legal framework hinders key stakeholders, such as legislators, from fully understanding the specific challenges obstructing data sharing and reuse in Europe. From the perspective of Can.Heal, one of the most significant recent legislative developments is the European Health Data Space (EHDS) Regulation. The EHDS represents the EU's response to the legal, infrastructural, and technical barriers preventing the full utilization of health and related data, including in research contexts. Its goal is to create a more streamlined legal framework that enables the lawful use of health data across various sectors, enhancing and complementing existing legislation. Additionally, it aims to improve data-sharing and reuse practices in Europe by promoting interoperable health data infrastructures and standardized data practices. Furthermore, the EHDS seeks to strengthen individuals' control and rights over their health data, complementing the protections already provided under the GDPR.

One critique of the EHDS is that it insufficiently considers how the newly introduced legal entities align with existing actors who have overlapping roles and responsibilities. This concern is particularly relevant in cases where EHDS actors have conflicting obligations with those of legal authorities under frameworks like the GDPR or national research ethics laws. Another important legal framework is the EU's Data Governance Act (DGA), which took effect in September 2023 but is not yet fully operational due to delayed national implementation by Member States. Once fully integrated, the DGA could provide a practical path for data-sharing initiatives through the creation of data altruism organizations. These organizations, which facilitate voluntary data sharing for public interest purposes (such as scientific research), offer a distinct governance framework and operate without financial gain. This includes the sharing of personal data, as outlined under the GDPR, and can either involve data altruism organizations processing the data themselves or making it available to third parties.

A further potential avenue for formalizing data-sharing initiatives is the European Digital Research Consortium (EDIC), introduced under the EU's Digital Decade Policy Programme 2030. The EDIC, inspired by the European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERICs), involves multi-country membership and joint establishment by multiple nations. Several European biomedical data-sharing projects, such as the 1+ Million Genomes Initiative and the European Federation for CANcer IMages (EUCAIM) project, are exploring the EDIC model. However, establishing an EDIC requires significant political and financial support from Member States, necessitating extensive lobbying and negotiations, followed by drafting detailed statutes and bylaws. At present, the EHDS does not offer a clear framework for the formal participation of EDICs in its ecosystem, though this issue is reportedly being addressed by lawmakers.

Despite the potential of the EHDS, DGA, and EDIC frameworks, considerable uncertainties remain, especially regarding their practical implementation. While Can.Heal does not aim to establish an entire data-sharing infrastructure, it seeks to develop an integrated approach to improving access for individuals, cancer patients and survivors, to cancer prevention, diagnosis, and treatment through personalized medicine. For that purpose, understanding the GDPR remains crucial, as it lays the

foundational regulatory framework for data sharing, while the EHDS and DGA rather broaden the possibilities for specific forms of data exchange.

GDPR: Scope and Application

Regulation 2016/679 of the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation or the GDPR) went into force in May 2016 and became applicable 2 years later. The GDPR's main scope is to protect natural persons in relation to the processing of personal data but also to allow the free movement of personal data in the EU. Article 8(1) of the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (Charter) and Article 16(1) of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU) provide that everyone has the right to the protection of personal data concerning him or her.²² Recital 4 of the GDPR, although not legally binding, lays foundations for data sharing by stating that the processing of personal data should be designed to serve mankind and further clarifies that the right to the protection of personal data is not an absolute right. This right must be considered in relation to its function in society and be balanced against other fundamental rights (e.g., right to the integrity of the person, the right to liberty and security, freedom of expression etc.) and public interests in accordance with the principle of necessity and proportionality.²³ Recital 4 of the GDPR suggests a need for equilibrium between data protection and other fundamental rights. Data protection is from another crucial viewpoint also a necessary condition for the effective exercise of other fundamental rights, freedoms and for effective disposal of one's autonomy.

General provisions of the GDPR (Articles 1-4) define the scope of the Regulation along three main axes: (1) types of data processed (the what), (2) parties subject to the Regulation (the who), and (3) the territorial scope (the where).

The principle of proportionality along with the general principles of the GDPR enumerated in the Article 5 (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, confidentiality, and accountability) create a strong framework for data protection on the one hand, and data utilisation on the other. Data use is also supported by Article 1(3) using negative phrasing - data protection should not impede the free movement of personal data. This clause primarily echoes a guiding principle of internal market law and can also be justified by the GDPR's aim to ensure the free flow of personal data within the EU. Article 1(3) does not specify the recipients of this negative obligation. It could be argued that this provision is directed at Member States and is intended to prevent them from enacting national laws that restrict the free movement of data.²⁴ However, Article 1(3) along with Article 9(4) have significant practical implications for the scope of

²² Recital 1 of the GDPR

²³ EDPS Guidelines on assessing the proportionality of measures that limit the fundamental rights to privacy and to the protection of personal data

²⁴ Hijmnas, in Kuner, Bygrave, Docksey, *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary*, Article 1 GDPR, p. 57 (Oxford University Press 2020).

national data protection laws implementing the GDPR, in situations where the GDPR permits a different level of protection. Individual Member States have a broad scope for regulations regarding genetic and health data. Article 9(4) provides that Member States may maintain or introduce conditions beyond those defined by the GDPR, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic, biometric, or health data.²⁵ Nevertheless, Art. 1(3) of the GDPR is to be interpreted that there cannot be any legal restriction that data must not leave the country based on the GDPR or national law based on data protection. This includes the national provisions based on Art. 9(4).

Genomic Data in the GDPR

Under the GDPR, certain personal data types are labelled as special or sensitive, warranting additional legal safeguards. While processing regular personal data is lawful if it aligns with Article 6's lawful basis, the processing of special category data is nevertheless in principle forbidden. It can only occur if the controller complies with one of the ten exceptions outlined in Article 9(2). This implies that processing sensitive personal data typically necessitates fulfilling two **cumulative criteria**:

1. The processing must have a lawful basis (i.e. one of the six legal bases outlined in Article 6), and;
2. It must fall within at least one of the 10 exceptions specified in Article 9(2).

In the health context, special categories of personal data include data that reveal racial or ethnic origin, data concerning health (the physical or mental health of a person, including the provision of health care services), data concerning sex life or sexual orientation, and genetic data and biometric data processed to uniquely identify a natural person. Genetic data is defined as personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person, providing unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person, and which result from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question. However, not every genetic data should be treated as a category of personal data for the GDPR, especially if they do not provide unique information about the physiology or the health of an individual (though whole genome sequence data would qualify on uniqueness grounds). If the genomic data is accompanied with a patient unique identifier or other unique (health) information, genomic research data would be covered by the legal provisions speaking to genetic data even when they separately might not be truly unique.²⁶ Most genetic data do provide information about the individual's genetic family, which may also fall within the "related to" realm of the GDPR.

²⁵ Fruzsina Molnár-Gábor, Julian Sellner, Sophia Pagil, Santa Slokenberga, Olga Tzortzatou-Nanopoulou, Katarina Nyström, Harmonization after the GDPR? Divergences in the rules for genetic and health data sharing in four member states and ways to overcome them by EU measures: Insights from Germany, Greece, Latvia and Sweden, *Seminars in Cancer Biology*, Volume 84, 2022

²⁶ Dove, E. S., "Collection and Protection of Genomic Data," in S. Gibbon et al., *Routledge Handbook of Genomics, Health and Society* (New York: Routledge, 2018), at 163-164.

While the GDPR defines genetic data²⁷ as a special category of personal data in Article 9, it does not refer to genomic data. Nevertheless, the definition of genetic data makes it clear that genomic data is included in the term. This means that the first and fundamental assessment when considering if genetic, genomic, or health data are governed by the GDPR is whether the data fulfils the definition of personal data. Personal data is any information relating to an identified or identifiable natural person. This explanation specifies that it is not necessary for a natural person or individual to be explicitly identified by the data. **It is sufficient that they are identifiable**, meaning they can be recognised either directly or indirectly from the data. Beyond the more evident identifiers like names, specific genetic factors are also considered as possible means for individual identification. However, this does not imply that genetic elements (as referred to in Art 4(1)) will invariably result in identification. Rather, they are merely one of the various elements that could facilitate the identification of a person. Art 4(1) delineates that in order to discern when genomic data are identifiable, a controller must evaluate if the data relate to an identified or identifiable natural person who can be identified directly or indirectly.²⁸ These notions are analysed sequentially, highlighting the specific challenges they present within the realm of genomics. The Breyer ruling by the European Court of Justice reinforces the broad interpretation adopted by courts regarding key definitions in EU data protection legislation. It emphasizes that personal data pertains to any individual who can be identified, be it directly or indirectly. This implies that certain information may be classified as personal data, even without pinpointing a particular individual. Additional guidance on determining identifiability is provided in Recital 26 of the GDPR. When evaluating if a person can be identified, it is necessary to consider all feasible methods that might be employed for identification, such as distinguishing the individual either by the data controller or another party. In judging whether such methods are likely to be used for identifying the individual, one must take all objective factors into account, including the cost and time needed for identification, as well as the technology available at the time of data processing and any advancements in technology.

A crucial criterion for information to be considered personal data is that it must have a connection to an individual. The Article 29 Working Party highlighted in their explanation of personal data that this connection is essential to determine whether the data are closely associated with an individual to the extent that they qualify as personal data. Often, the nature of the information itself will be evidently related to an individual, for instance, results from a medical genetic test are undeniably concerning the individual tested. However, other information may not obviously be about a person but related to the person, and therefore result in an impact on their rights and interests. Therefore, it is necessary to focus on the purpose, content, and effect of the data.²⁹ The interpretation of when data relate to an individual may be important in the genomic context. Just as it is uncontroversial that medical records and healthcare data are obviously about an individual, in many uses of genetic, genomic, or health

²⁷ Article 4(13) of the GDPR defines genetic data in a broad manner, meaning “personal data relating to the inherited or acquired genetic characteristics of a natural person which give unique information about the physiology or the health of that natural person and which result, in particular, from an analysis of a biological sample from the natural person in question”.

²⁸ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Opinion 4/2007 on the concept of personal data. 2007

²⁹ Case C-434/16 Peter Nowak v Data Protection Commissioner [2017] ECR I-994

data, it will be obvious that data relate to a person. Genomic or genetic data, which is one of the special categories of data alongside biometric data, is frequently referred to as highly identifying data. Therefore, the purposes or effects of processing such data impact individuals' rights and interests and may be important in determining if data could be considered personal. This is relevant for the question if the genome of person A forms personal data of a sibling of A (or other relative).

In the context of Can.Heal, it is necessary to emphasise that GDPR applies to the processing of personal data of living persons (natural persons). Personal data concerning deceased persons is beyond the scope of the GDPR. Due to the nature of the Can.Heal project, it is necessary for the relevant institutions involved in genomic data processing to consult the applicable national data protection laws which may impose certain restrictions and/or compliance obligations in relation to processing data from deceased persons. It should be expected that some of the biological samples and their associated data will be from deceased donors. Recital 27 of the GDPR allows Member States to adopt rules regarding the processing of personal data of deceased persons. Some EU Member States have independently enacted post-mortem data protection legislation and allow post-mortem control by relatives (e.g., in terms of access, rectification, or deletion)³⁰. In general, the ethical acceptability of utilising and disseminating personal data after a participant's death is debatable, especially when consent for post-mortem data usage has not been obtained. This raises the question if such data should be prohibited from use, or conversely, should constraints be lifted due to the perceived lack of potential harm to the deceased and potential benefit for others. This issue is especially pertinent in the context of the usage of genetic data. Given the sensitive and distinctly identifiable characteristics of genetic data, there is a risk that privacy and discrimination issues could affect the living relatives of the deceased.

A broad way personal data is defined by the GDPR also encompasses pseudonymised data. Pseudonymisation is encouraged as a safeguard for data, especially for scientific research, throughout the GDPR. Besides, it is emphasised in Recital 29 that it should be possible for one controller to separate personal data and any additional information internally to a satisfactory standard, providing the controller has taken technical and organisational measures. A typical simple pseudonymisation procedure consists of the separation of identifiers in a secure but reversible way (Art 4(5) of the GDPR).

Sharing anonymised data may be sufficient for some scientific research purposes, which would reduce the legal compliance burden, but many scientific objectives require rich data in pseudonymised form. Article 89(1) of the GDPR holds that safeguards shall ensure technical and organisational measures are in place to uphold the principle of data minimisation and goes on to highlight some measures which may be used to achieve this principle, such as pseudonymisation or anonymisation. Pseudonymised personal data cannot be considered equivalent to anonymised data "as they continue to allow an individual data subject to be singled out and linkable across different data sets". The

³⁰ Bak, M.A.R., Ploem, M.C., Ateşyürek, H. et al. Stakeholders' perspectives on the post-mortem use of genetic and health-related data for research: a systematic review. *Eur J Hum Genet* 28, 403–416 (2020). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-019-0503-5>

feasibility of re-identifications should be assessed contextually, taking into account the “means reasonably likely to be used [...] to identify the natural person directly or indirectly” (GDPR Recital 26). Importantly, Recital 26 explicitly states that this condition is not limited to the party who is provided with the pseudonymised data and is also applicable to the cases where re-identification of data subjects can be carried out by another person, i.e., a third party. Pseudonymity is likely to allow for identifiability, and therefore stays inside the scope of the legal regime of data protection.³¹

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) Genomic data falls in most situations under the definition of special categories of personal data. For processing special categories of personal data, it is necessary to have a legal basis under Article 6(1) and an exemption from the general prohibition of processing genetic data under Article 9(2).**
- 2) Genomic data is not personal only under condition that it does not relate to an individual. For example, a single genetic variant/SNP that is common in the reference population, can be considered non-personal data, provided that it is not associated with other forms of information that can be used to trace it back to a unique individual. Pseudonymised genomic data is still personal data and GDPR applies.**
- 3) Even though GDPR applies to living individuals’ data, genomic data of a deceased person could still relate to another identifiable living relative, and therefore it is still personal data. Member state countries may have adopted rules related to processing data of deceased persons.**
- 4) It is necessary to be mindful of the Article 9(4) which allows Member States to introduce further conditions, including limitations, with regard to the processing of genetic data, biometric data or data concerning health. Many countries have done so.**

Parties Subject to the Regulation

The GDPR has significantly influenced data sharing and transfers among institutions in several ways. One key aspect is the necessity to designate GDPR roles—such as controller, joint controller, and processor—among the parties involved and to clarify their respective compliance obligations. The roles of controller, processor, joint controller, along with the concept of third party are key to the application of the GDPR as they determine who is responsible for protecting personal data and how data subjects may exercise their rights. **Controllers are accountable for ensuring respect of GDPR principles and demonstrating compliance.** This accountability cannot be delegated. Processors have more limited statutory obligations, namely that they must only process data according to the

³¹ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party (2014) Opinion 05/2014 on Anonymisation Techniques. 0829/14/EN. WP216

documented instructions of the controller.³² It is essential to accurately assign these roles to entities handling personal data because it greatly affects their responsibilities towards each other, individuals whose data is processed, and regulatory authorities. The importance of and the difficulties involved in defining GDPR roles among various parties become especially evident in complex processing environments involving multiple parties. In this chapter the GDPR roles are explained along with examples of the roles in the Can.Heal consortium.

Controller

Article 4(7) of the GDPR defines the controller as “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, **determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data**”.

The status under GDPR depends on control over the processing activities rather than control over the personal data itself. An entity can qualify as a controller through legal designation or actual (factual and functional) control.³³

- 1) Implicit legal competence means a law establishes a task or imposes a duty on an entity to collect and process certain data for the purpose determined by the law. Article 4(7) specifies that when the purposes and means of processing are determined by Union or Member State law, the controller or the criteria for its designation may be established by that law. If the controller is explicitly identified by law, this will be decisive in determining who acts as the controller. This implies that the legislator has designated as controller the entity with a genuine ability to exercise control. In some countries, national law assigns public authorities the responsibility for processing personal data within the scope of their duties. This could, for instance, be the case for certain state-run health data registries, or a public hospital. Where data sharing hubs are established by Member State legislation, legislation assigns controller status to different actors.
- 2) **The concepts of controller and processor are functional concepts.** They aim to allocate responsibilities according to the actual roles of the parties. This implies that the legal status of a controller must, in principle, be determined by its actual activities in a specific situation rather than upon the formal designation of an actor as being either a controller or processor (e.g. in a contract). All relevant factual circumstances must be taken into account to reach a

³² Becker, Regina, Adrian Thorogood, Jasper Bovenberg, Colin Mitchell, and Alison Hall. 2022. “Applying GDPR Roles and Responsibilities to Scientific Data Sharing.” *International Data Privacy Law* 12 (3): 207–19. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipac011>.

³³ *ibid*

conclusion as to whether a particular entity exercises a determinative influence with respect to the processing of personal data in question.³⁴

With respect to determining purposes, the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) notes that the interpretation is relatively straightforward: **only the controller can choose a purpose for which data is processed**. A processor cannot pursue an independent purpose for processing, otherwise it no longer qualifies as a processor and should be considered as a controller for the processing operation for which it determined the purpose. The EDPB identifies some key questions for identifying the control: “why is this processing taking place?”, “who decided that the processing should take place for a particular purpose?”, and who “actually exerts a decisive influence on the purpose and means of the processing?”

Article 4(7) acknowledges that the purposes and means of the processing can be determined by multiple actors. It specifies that the controller is the entity that alone or jointly with others decides the purposes and means of the processing. Consequently, several entities can act as controllers for the same processing, each being subject to the relevant data protection regulations. An organisation can still be considered a controller even if it does not make all the decisions regarding the purposes and means. The criteria for joint controllership and the extent to which multiple actors share control can vary. The EDPB recognizes a further distinction between essential means (which are determined by the controller) and non-essential means (which may be determined by a processor). Essential means are closely tied to the purpose and scope of the processing and are typically reserved for the controller. Examples include the type of personal data processed (“which data shall be processed?”), the duration of processing (“for how long shall they be processed?”), the categories of recipients (“who shall have access to them?”), and the categories of data subjects (“whose personal data are being processed?”). On the other hand, non-essential means pertain to more practical aspects of implementation, such as the choice of specific hardware or software and detailed security measures, which may be left to the processor to decide.

In regard to determining means of processing, the EDPB recognises that in practice, processors acting at the request of controllers may exercise certain discretion as to how the data will be processed to achieve the purpose specified by the controller. Consequently, both the controller and the processor may participate in defining the means of processing. Despite the extensive guidance and numerous examples provided by the EDPB, it acknowledges that assigning GDPR roles can still be challenging in certain data processing environments. This is particularly true for complex research-oriented ecosystems like the network of institutions supported by genomic infrastructures. Therefore, determining GDPR roles within a genomic data sharing process will be crucial for ensuring compliance, with the outcome being influenced by the specific context of each processing operation.

³⁴ European Data Protection Board. 2020. “Guidelines 07/2020 on the Concepts of Controller and Processor in the GDPR.” 07/2020. https://edpb.europa.eu/our-work-tools/documents/public-consultations/2020/guidelines-072020-concepts-controller-and_en.

Possible Can.Heal scenario in bilateral data transfer from the data provider to the data user for the purpose of research study of a data user:

Example of stakeholders:

Hospital or research cohort owner (data provider)

Research organisation (data user)

Table 1. GDPR roles under a bilateral data transfer

	Processing operation	Data provider	Data user
1.	Genomic data storage for primary clinical purposes at the data provider	Controller	Not involved
2.	Accepting the data-user’s study design and data transfer (data transfer = even disclosing data on data provider servers to the data user; there may not be any movement of the data involved)	Controller	Third Party
3.	Data storage by the data user	Not involved	Controller
4.	Data use for envisaged research study by the data user	Not involved	Controller
5.	Data deletion after the research study is finished (i.e., results are published)	Not involved	Controller

Joint Controllers

As mentioned in the previous paragraph, GDPR defines the controller as “a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, **determines the purposes and means** of the processing of personal data”. Implied in this definition is the possibility of more than one party acting as a controller under the GDPR. Article 26 of the GDPR, which aligns with the definition in Article 4(7), states that "where two or more controllers jointly determine the purposes and means of processing, they shall be joint controllers." In general, joint controllership arises in relation to a specific processing activity when multiple parties collaboratively decide the purposes and means of that activity. Thus, determining whether joint controllers exist involves assessing if the determination of the purposes and means, which characterizes a controller, is made by more than one party. The term "jointly" should be understood as "together with" or "not alone," in various forms and combinations.

The assessment of joint controllership should be based on a factual analysis of the actual influence over the purposes and means of processing rather than on a formal one. All existing or proposed arrangements should be examined in light of the factual circumstances surrounding the relationship between the parties. A purely formal criterion is insufficient for at least two reasons. First, the formal designation of a joint controller—established by law or contract—might be absent, and second, the formal designation may not accurately reflect the reality of the arrangements, potentially assigning

the role of the controller to an entity that is not actually in a position to determine the purposes and means of processing. Not all processing activities involving multiple entities result in joint controllership, since the key criterion for joint controllership is the joint participation of two or more entities in determining the purposes and means of a processing operation.

There is an intrinsic uncertainty about whether one has sufficient control over the processing of data by another party, especially where genetic or clinical data are not held or used by one party in an identifiable form but are part of a broader enterprise (e.g. a large-scale sequencing project with separated clinical and research elements). If one influences, creates an opportunity, encourages, or coordinates the processing of personal data by another party, there is a strong likelihood that the person is jointly determining the purposes and means of that data processing. Formal agreements are not required to establish joint control. One implication of joint control is that the controllers must determine their respective responsibilities for GDPR compliance (as per Article 26) and communicate these to the data subject. Importantly, joint controllers are jointly and severally liable for all obligations under the GDPR. In the context of genomics, where multiple collaborators often handle data in various forms as part of a collective endeavour, it is likely that many professionals and institutions will meet the criteria for joint control.

The involvement of multiple actors in the same processing activity does not automatically mean they act as joint controllers. Not every partnership, collaboration, or cooperation results in joint controllership, as this designation requires a case-by-case evaluation of the specific processing activity, and the exact role of each entity involved. For instance, if two entities exchange the same data without jointly determining the purposes or means of processing, this should be viewed as a transfer of data between separate controllers. Similarly, joint controllership is not applicable when multiple entities use a shared database or common infrastructure, provided each entity independently decides its own purposes. Additionally, in cases where different actors process the same personal data in a sequence of operations, with each actor having an independent purpose and means for their part of the process, joint controllership is excluded. In such scenarios, where there is no joint involvement in deciding the purposes and means of the same processing operation, the actors must be considered independent controllers operating successively. It is possible for the same party to act as a controller for certain processing operations while being a processor for other processing operations with respect to the same data subject or the same data.

Possible Can.Heal scenario e.g., where both data holder and data user design a study in a collaborative manner. In such case both institutions are joint controllers, since they both play a critical role in determining the purposes and essential means of processing.

Example of stakeholders:

Hospital or research cohort owner (data provider)

Research organisation (data user)

Table 2. GDPR roles under a bilateral data transfer: research collaboration

	Processing operation	Data provider	Data user
1.	Genomic data storage for primary clinical purposes at the data provider	Controller	Not involved
2.	Data storage of the data relevant for the joint research study of data provider and data user	Joint Controller	Joint Controller
3.	Data use for a completely different research study by the data user	Not involved	Controller
4.	Data use for the joint research study	Joint Controller	Joint Controller
5.	Data deletion after the joint research study is finished (i.e., results are published)	Joint Controller	Joint Controller

Processor

A processor, as defined in Article 4(8) of the GDPR, is a natural or legal person, public authority, agency, or any other body that processes personal data on behalf of the controller. Similar to the definition of a controller, the term "processor" encompasses a wide range of actors, meaning that any type of entity—whether an organisation or an individual—can take on the role of a processor. Processors can be held liable or fined if they fail to meet these obligations, or if they act outside the lawful instructions of the controller.

The role of a processor is defined not by the type of entity processing the data but by the specific activities it performs in a given context. Whether a processing activity qualifies as processing personal data on behalf of a controller under the GDPR depends on the nature of the service provided. In practice, if the service is not primarily focused on processing personal data, or if processing personal data is not a central aspect of the service, the service provider may have the ability to independently determine the purposes and means of that processing. In such cases, the service provider should be considered a separate controller, not a processor.

Processing personal data may involve multiple processors. For example, a controller may choose to engage different processors at various stages of processing, or it may engage one processor, who, with the controller's authorisation, brings in other sub-processors. The scope of the processing activity assigned to a processor can be very specific or more general and extensive.

To qualify as a processor, two key conditions must be met:

- a) The processor must be a separate entity from the controller;
- b) It must process personal data on behalf of the controller.

Being a separate entity means that the controller delegates all or part of the processing activities to an external organisation. For instance, within a group of institutions, one company can act as a processor

for another company that is the controller, as they are separate entities. However, a department within a company generally cannot be a processor for another department within the same organisation.

If a controller decides to process data internally, using its own resources, such as its own staff, this does not constitute a processor relationship. Employees and other individuals acting under the direct authority of the controller, such as temporary staff, are not considered processors since they process personal data as part of the controller's entity. According to Article 29, they are also bound by the controller's instructions.

Possible Can.Heal scenario involving more complex environment where data transfer is mediated through a platform for genomic data sharing. Since the data sharing environment is already complex and there are significant uncertainties stemming from context and the choice of possible platform, is this table rather illustrative.

Example of stakeholders:

Research cohort owner (data provider)

Platform

Research organisation (data user)

Table 3. GDPR roles under a platform-mediated data transfer

	Processing operation	Data provider	Platform	Data user
1.	Transfer of the genomic data to the platform	Controller	Processor	Not involved
2.	Data storage of the data relevant for the joint research study of data provider and user	Joint Controller	Processor or controller	Joint Controller
3.	Data storage conducted by the data provider	Controller	Processor or controller	Not involved
4.	Data disclosure (granting access to the data user)	Controller	Processor or controller	Third party
5.	Data analysis for research (depending on the existence of shared purpose for the analysis)	Joint Controller or Not involved	Processor or controller	Joint Controller or Controller

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) **Be mindful that the concepts of controller and processor are functional concepts. They aim to allocate responsibilities according to the actual roles of the parties irrespective of contractual terms.**
- 2) **GDPR roles have significant implications for the parties' obligations vis-a-vis one another, data subjects, and the regulators.**

- 3) **Only controllers determine the purposes and means of the processing. There can be several joint controllers if they determine the purposes and means of the processing together.**
- 4) **There is not a “controller for the data” but a “controller for the processing”. Be mindful of the controller-oriented view (see next chapter).**
- 5) **Defining the purpose of the processing does not necessarily mean having access to the data. It is possible to be a controller without having touched the data at any point. In such cases, data may be handled by a processor who does not influence the purpose or the essential means. The processor processes the data on behalf of the controller and could only influence the non-essential means (e.g., in case of analysis to choose software A instead of B, but not to choose method of analysis – simple statistics vs. machine learning).**
- 6) **Key to controllership is dissecting the processing chain and defining where the processing for a certain purpose starts and ends. Parties might find themselves in many roles and these may change during the data lifecycle activities. That is why there is controllership for processing and not for the data itself.**

Secondary Use and Further Processing

Sharing of genetic and genomic data, especially that generated within the healthcare context, is fraught with challenges, not least structural, technical, ethical, legal and regulatory considerations. As such, data sharing is at a critical juncture in the advancement of genomic medicine and its impact on patient care.³⁵ One of the first questions we should ask from the legal point of view should be: what sharing of genomic data and related terms stand for in the European context? Secondary use of data, data reuse, data repurposing, data recycling, data recontextualisation, or data sharing are not terms defined in the GDPR. Several authors have sought to differentiate these, and other semantically related terms based on a variety of factors.³⁶ In general, the frequently used term “secondary use” refers to the following situations:

1. The change of the purpose of the data (the purpose for which the data was created (primary purpose) is significantly different from the purpose of its further use, regardless of whether the data is held by the same person)³⁷

³⁵ Raza S., Hall A. Genomic medicine and data sharing. *Br Med Bull.* 2017 Sep 1;123(1):35-45. doi: 10.1093/bmb/ldx024. PMID: 28910995; PMCID: PMC5862236.

³⁶ Custers, Bart and Vrabec, Helena, *Big Data and Data Reuse: A Taxonomy of Data Reuse for Balancing Big Data Benefits and Personal Data Protection* (2016). *International Data Privacy Law*, 2016, Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3046774>

³⁷ Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It “Further Processing” Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?. *European Journal of Health Law*, 30(2), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

or

2. transfer of the data among other controllers (the exchange of personal data with other controllers who intend to use the data for their own purposes).

Data sharing on the other hand could mean:

1. Transfer of the personal data outside the EU (the transfer of personal data outside the EU/EEA is subject to a specific set of rules under the GDPR).^{38 39}
2. Transfer of the data within/between organisation(s) whether or not using data sharing intermediaries.

Differentiating these and other semantically related terms has a significant impact on the ability to engage in the intended (further) processing and on being compliant with the GDPR.

Further processing

Although the GDPR does not explicitly refer to the secondary use of data, the closest concept used in the regulation is the further processing of personal data. The GDPR's non-legally binding Recital 50 already outlines the limitations of further processing and provides a terminological framework for it. Further processing of personal data should only be allowed when compatible with the purposes for which the personal data were originally collected. The distinction between further processing and primary processing is necessary because further processing generally imposes additional obligations on the controller which, if not complied with, expose the controller to the risk of sanctions.

According to Article 6(4) of the GDPR, data can only be further processed for a purpose different from the one that motivated data collection if it is compatible with that original purpose. This reflects the principle of purpose limitation. Specifically, Article 5(1)(b) states that “personal data shall be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes”. However, when it comes to research, Article 5(1)(b) provides a special exemption for research activities. It states that further processing for scientific research purposes, in line with Article 89(1), is not seen as incompatible with the original purpose. Nonetheless, it is important to note that the EDPS, drawing from Recital 159 of the GDPR, differentiates between genuine research and other forms of research. This distinction is crucial, as genuine research must adhere to methodological standards, uphold research integrity, aim to benefit the common good to grow society’s collective knowledge and wellbeing, knowledge creation, and

³⁸ PHG Foundation of the University of Cambridge, The GDPR and Genomic Data: The Impact of the GDPR and DPA 2018 on Genomic Healthcare and Research (May 2020); www.phgfoundation.org/documents/gdpr-andgenomic-data-report.pdf.

³⁹ Bovenberg, J., et al., How to fix the GDPR's frustration of global biomedical research. *Science* 370,40-42(2020).DOI:10.1126/science.abd2499

reliance on the safeguards commonly utilised in the research context, such as an ethics review process and scientific codes of conduct.⁴⁰

Only a specific legal provision can serve as a valid legal basis for overriding the purpose limitation principle stemming from the Article 5(1)(b). For EU or Member State lawmakers, Article 23 further outlines the necessary requirements and conditions that such a law must satisfy. Article 6(4) allows i) legal provisions or ii) data subject consent as a valid basis for further processing that is incompatible with the original purpose. The explicit mention of consent in Article 6(4) as a basis for incompatible further processing implies recognition that data subjects can waive a fundamental right if they consent. When either of these two conditions is fulfilled, data can be processed irrespective of the compatibility.

If the controller cannot rely on data subject's consent, Union or Member State law or does not meet the criteria for compatibility for scientific research⁴¹, which are exemptions allowing further processing irrespective of compatibility, it must perform a formal compatibility assessment of the intended further processing activity. This assessment process, outlined in Article 6(4) and further explained in Recital 50 of the GDPR, is designed to determine whether the further processing aligns with the purpose for which the data was originally collected and provides the legal framework for the compatibility test, which involves evaluating several factors to decide whether further processing is compatible (with the purpose for which the controller has collected the data).⁴² These factors include:

- The link between purposes (Article 6(4)(a)): The controller shall consider the connection between the original purpose of data collection and the purpose of the further processing.
- The context in which data was collected (Article 6(4)(b)): The controller shall assess the context in which the data was originally collected, including the relationship between the data subject and the controller. For instance, if the data subject would reasonably expect their data to be used for the new purpose, this can be a positive factor in the assessment.
- The nature of the data (Article 6(4)(c)): The controller shall take the nature of the data into account, particularly if it involves special categories of data (e.g., sensitive data like health information). Further processing of such data typically requires a higher level of protection.
- The impact on data subjects (Article 6(4)(d)): The controller shall evaluate the potential impact on data subjects, particularly in terms of privacy risks and rights.

⁴⁰ European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS), A Preliminary Opinion on Data Protection and Scientific Research, January 2020.

⁴¹ Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR.

⁴² Compatibility of purposes is one of the criteria for "permissibility". Further processing may be deemed compatible with the original purpose (i.e., compliant with the purpose limitation principle), but still not permissible/allowed/legal because another GDPR (or some other legal) requirement is not met.

- Safeguards (Article 6(4)(e)): The controller shall assess the safeguards in place to ensure the protection of the data (e.g., encryption, anonymisation,) during further processing.

Considering these factors and concluding processing as compatible means the controller complies with the purpose limitation principle. However that is only one factor of the overall GDPR compliance assessment. Furthermore, after a favourable result from the compatibility assessment, the data controller may need to inform the data subject about the intended further processing before proceeding. These obligations are specified in Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR and represent additional requirements that the data controller must fulfil when engaging in further processing of personal data. Even where further processing meets the criteria for compatibility, it may still not be legally permissible due to other constraints (e.g., permission by Italian supervisory authority Garante in Italy).

Data-Focused View

Finally, one key distinction between secondary use and further processing under the GDPR is the focus on the data lifecycle, which is divided in two approaches: the data-focused view and the controller-focused view. In order to navigate the secondary use of data, it is necessary to keep in mind both the data-focused view, which explains the flow of data, and the controller-focused view, which sheds light on the roles of individual parties within the data flows ecosystem, and their obligations in processing data. The roles (controller, joint controller, processor) are linked to the responsibility for processing the data. Primarily, knowledge of the rules of further processing, especially the ability to identify the persons responsible for the processed data, is essential for the compliance of data handling with the GDPR.

In the data-focused view, processing for an additional purpose involves the entire data lifecycle, from data creation to deletion. Genomic data could be reused in many ways, from the simplest secondary use by one institution in one country to controlled access/sharing on international federated platforms with different internal solutions and sharing rules. All these different solutions have in common the obligation to comply with the GDPR rules when the data subjects are located on the territory of the European Union.

The following table shows difference between further processing and secondary use of data on an example from Denmark, where the Danish National Genome Centre (NGC),⁴³ established in 2019 manages the Danish National Genome Database (NGD), which includes providing access to the genomic data stored in the database for scientific purposes.⁴⁴ At the same time, there is a statutory obligation to submit patient genomic data to the database that has been generated for the purpose of diagnosis or treatment.⁴⁵

⁴³ For more information see <https://www.eng.ngc.dk/research-and-international-collaboration> (accessed 15 January 2024)

⁴⁴ Laugesen K, Mengel-From J, Christensen K, et al. A Review of Major Danish Biobanks: Advantages and Possibilities of Health Research in Denmark. *Clin Epidemiol.* 2023;15:213-239. Published 2023 Feb 21. doi:10.2147/CLEP.S392416

⁴⁵ Bekendtgørelse af sundhedsloven, Chapter 68, available at: <https://www.retsinformation.dk/eli/Ita/2023/248>.

Table 4. Examples of data processing activities involving genomic data previously collected by the data controller

Processing activity	Further processing? (controller- focused view)	Secondary use? (data-focused view)
<p>A healthcare facility diagnoses a reportable disease to the NGD based on genetic analysis (reporting is automatic or manual).</p> <p>Processing activities:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Patient data collection 2. Sending data to NGD by a healthcare facility 3. Collection of data by NGC 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No. Primary and only purpose is a patient diagnosis. 2. Yes. Even without the obligation to submit the information to the NGD, this data would be used by the health facility for primary diagnostic purposes. 3. No. NGC is the institution responsible for collecting information for the NGD. Therefore, it is its primary purpose. 	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. No. Primary and only purpose is a patient diagnosis. 2. Ambiguous. Diagnosis is a prerequisite and integral part of the obligation to report to the NGD and, therefore, the second purpose cannot be separated from the first one. It can be, however, distinguished. The processing of data for diagnosis and treatment is the primary purpose in this case. Data processing for submission to the NGD is a secondary purpose (In many cases it is difficult to distinguish the primary from the secondary or the essential from the non-essential purpose). 3. Yes. NGD is not a primary source in terms of data generation.

Controller-Focused View

The controller-focused view considers specific phases within the data lifecycle, defined by who is processing the data and for what purpose. From this perspective, each phase begins when a controller collects personal data—either directly from the data subject or, in the case of pre-existing data, from another source and concludes when the controller's intended purpose for collecting the data is fulfilled.⁴⁶ The GDPR primarily tracks the actors responsible for processing data. Hence, tracking only the data may be misleading as the regulation primarily implements its goal of protecting the fundamental rights and freedoms of natural persons, in particular their right to data protection, by mandating that **there must be a person responsible for the data at every point of the data lifecycle.**

In complex processing environments involving multiple parties across different phases of the data lifecycle, the question of "who is the data controller?" becomes less relevant without additional context. Therefore, a more precise question would be: "who is the controller for a specific processing operation?" There may be up to four controllers throughout the genomic data lifecycle, each corresponding to the processing operations required for completing the four phases. A four-step model of the data lifecycle offers a useful framework for accurately identifying controllers at different stages of genomic data reuse lifecycle. These groups of controllers are labelled as follows: CTI (Controller for initial data collection), CTA (Controller for making data available via e.g. cBioPortal), CTD (Controller for data disclosure to a specific user), and CTU (Controller for the (re)use of the data).

Table 5. Possible categories of controllers across the data reuse lifecycle

Party	Controller for what activity?	Examples of processing operations
CTI	Initial collection of personal data and its primary use.	Data collection directly from the data subject (e.g., patient intake questionnaires). - Data generation by analysing biological samples provided by a patient or research participant. - Using the data for the specific medical (e.g., diagnostic/treatment) or research purpose pursued by CTI (i.e., primary use).
CTA	Making the data widely available for a secondary use on the data sharing platform.	Generating aggregated metadata to aid discoverability (e.g., through the cBioPortal) by CTUs. - Data cleaning, structuring, and curating to defined standards/formats, or otherwise making it ready for a reuse. - Transfer of the data to an external Data Hub or another type of SPE, or, if retaining the data on premise.

⁴⁶ Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It “Further Processing” Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?. *European Journal of Health Law*, 30(2), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

		- Implementing a local instance of an SPE, allowing remote access and/or querying of the data by CTUs.
CTD	Disclosing data to a particular data user (or otherwise granting permission to use the data).	All operations needed to enable data use by the CTU. Depending on the architectural pattern of the Data Hub, SPE or other data infrastructure service provider relied upon by the CTD, this may entail any of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Data transfer to the CTU - Granting access to the relevant sub-set of the data in a dedicated digital workspace on an SPE - Generating a digital token that the CTU can use to instruct the SPE to perform a federated/distributed analysis - Approving a bespoke data analysis algorithm brought to the SPE by the CTU.
CTU	Controller for using the data for an own (approved) purpose.	All data processing operations needed to achieve the purpose(s) pursued by the CTU, specified by the CTU in the data access request, (and approved by the CTD).

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) Only rules of further processing have relevance for GDPR compliance when using genomic data for other than its primary purpose.**
- 2) Every new purpose must have its own justification (legal basis). No processing should take place before the actual purpose is identified and a suitable legal basis found.**
- 3) Further processing is always performed by a data controller that has already collected the data for another purpose, as opposed to a controller that is requesting access to the data to process them for its own (primary) purpose.**
- 4) When personal data are shared with an external party which is not necessary for the purpose the data were initially collected by the controller, it is further processing and the controller must perform a compatibility test, unless having consent from the data subject to do so or there is a national or EU law allowing to do that. This is the case of incidental findings (reporting back from researcher to clinician constitutes further processing).**
- 5) Sharing of the data among independent controllers does not necessarily constitute further processing. This is the case when data is collected with the purpose to make it available for external parties (e.g. biobanks). This does not mean that parties in e.g. project consortiums can all rely on one member’s legal basis. Each controller must have its own legal basis (be legally allowed to process personal data).**

Data Subjects' Rights

Even if there are all appropriate technical and organisational measures in place to ensure personal data are processed safely and lawfully, the human aspect is always a priority. That means that not only the data, but foremost the data subjects need to be protected, which means fairness, transparency, and accountability principles need to be ensured and promoted, which cannot be achieved without data subjects' rights being respected. However, fundamental right, including data subject rights, are not absolute which poses issues on striking balance between various fundamental rights protected by the Union's legal order or finding balance among the conflicting interests of data controllers, public and the data subjects. GDPR is aware of that and contains several exemptions, limitations and derogations to the data subjects' rights to ensure its both missions, i.e. not only to protect personal data, but also to enable its free movement and further use.

The fundamental need for private life is inherent in a human being and extends to many areas in life. However, there is no universally accepted definition of privacy. When a privacy claim is recognised in a law or in a social convention, such as constitutions or international agreements, they speak of privacy rights.⁴⁷ Chapter III of the GDPR (Arts. 12-23), which relates to the rights of the data subject, lays down a set of specific rights, alongside the conditions for their applicability and potential exemptions or derogations, afforded by the Regulation to data subjects.

The GDPR outlines eight key subjective rights, organised into three categories:⁴⁸

- (1) Information and access to personal data;
- (2) Rectification and erasure;
- (3) The right to object and automated decision-making.

Ensuring individuals are informed is essential for obtaining valid consent and exercising control over their data (Articles 13 and 14). The right to information continues throughout the data processing phase, allowing individuals to access their data and additional details at any time (Article 15). The second category emphasizes the rights to erasure and rectification. The right to erasure, often called the right to be forgotten, allows individuals to request the deletion of their data and prevent further use when consent is revoked, or the data is no longer necessary for the purpose it was collected (Article 17). Individuals also have the right to demand corrections or restrictions on data processing. Additionally, the GDPR introduced the right to data portability, enabling individuals to obtain and transfer their data between service providers (Article 20). Lastly, the GDPR provides individuals with the right to object to data processing (Article 21) and to avoid decisions made solely through automated processes (Article 22). These rights aim to reduce the negative impact of profiling, particularly when used for individual profiling purposes. However, these control rights may be limited in certain situations, such as for national security (Article 23). Some rights have specific limitations,

⁴⁷ Alan F Westin, 'Social and Political Dimensions of Privacy' (2003) 59 *Journal of Social Issues* 431.

⁴⁸ Vrabec, H. U. (2021). *Data subject rights under the GDPR: With a commentary through the lens of the data-driven economy*. Oxford University Press.

such as data portability, which applies only to data processed automatically and under a legal basis like a contract or consent (Article 20(1)(a), (b)).

In the context of data processing for research purposes, the following rights of the data subject are of relevance in the GDPR:

- Right to be informed (Arts. 13 and 14)
- Right of access (Art. 15)
- Right to rectification (Art. 16)
- Right to erasure (also called the right to be forgotten) (Art. 17)
- Right to restriction of processing (Art. 18)
- Right to data portability (Art. 20)
- Right to object (Art. 21)

Right to Be Informed

Although data subject rights are generally considered equal, the right to information stands out in practice as it embodies the principle of transparency and serves as the foundation for all other rights. The obligation to inform data subjects about the processing of their personal data is particularly crucial because it directly influences their ability to exercise the other rights, such as the right to access and rectify their data and the right to object to its processing.⁴⁹ The right to be informed is strongly rooted in the principles of autonomy and fairness and is extensively covered in several articles of the GDPR, such as in Articles 13 and 14.

The GDPR underscores the importance of providing data subjects with clear, concise, and meaningful information about data processing in a timely manner. Recital 58 reinforces this by stating that “*the principle of transparency requires [...] any information addressed to the public or to the data subject be concise, easily accessible, and easy to understand, using clear and plain language and, where appropriate, visualisation.*” Additionally, Recital 39 highlights the need for individuals to be informed about the risks, rules, safeguards, and rights related to the processing of their personal data and how to exercise these rights. The right to information is strongly intertwined with transparency as a fundamental value. In both the private and the public sectors, transparency serves the objectives of legitimate governance. The right to information is not standalone but integrated into a comprehensive data protection framework within the broader EU legal system. While this framework may not grant individuals absolute control, it does offer one of the most detailed and extensive data protection mechanisms available.

Articles 13 and 14 detail the specific information that controllers must communicate to data subjects prior to engaging in the intended processing, and by considering two scenarios: (1) when data is collected directly from the data subject and (2) when data is obtained from third parties. Although the disclosure requirements under the two articles overlap to a significant extent, they also contain several

⁴⁹ Judgment of the European Court of Justice C- 201/ 14, Bara.

differences that reflect the circumstances specific to each data collection context. Notably, when data is not collected directly from the data subject, there is an additional requirement to describe the categories of data involved (Article 14(1)(d)). This requirement likely exists because, in such cases, the data subject may have limited awareness or control over the data being reused. By detailing the categories, the data subject gains a clearer understanding of the nature and scope of the processing. In the second scenario where the data is obtained from other sources rather than from the data subject, the data controller must disclose the sources of the data and, if applicable, indicate whether the data was drawn from publicly accessible sources (Article 14(2)(f)).

The table below summarises the types of information disclosure requirements under Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR.

Table 6. Information disclosure requirements for controllers towards their data subjects

Type of information to be provided	Article 13 *	Article 14 **
Name and Contact details of Controllers	Required	Required
Name and Contact Details of Representative	If Applicable	If Applicable
Name and Contact Details of DPO	If Applicable	If Applicable
Purpose of Processing	Required	Required
Lawful Basis for Processing	Required	Required
Legitimate Interests for Processing	If Applicable	If Applicable
Categories of Personal Data Obtained	Not Required	Required
Recipients or Categories of Recipients of Data	If Applicable	If Applicable
Transfer of Data to Third Countries	If Applicable	If Applicable
Retention Period	Required	Required
Right(s) Available to Data Subjects	Required	Required
Right to Withdraw Consent	If Applicable	If Applicable
Right to Lodge a Complaint with a Supervisory Authority	Required	Required
Source of the Personal Data	Not Required	Required
Information Regarding Automated Decision-Making Profiling	If Applicable	If Applicable
Adapted from Kindylidi & de Barros, 2021 ⁵⁰ *Article 13 requirements do not apply if the relevant controller can demonstrate that the data subject already has the information ** Article 14 requirements do not apply if the relevant controller can demonstrate that one of the conditions under Art. 14(5) GDPR is met		

⁵⁰ Kindylidi, Iakovina, and Inês Antas de Barros. 2021. "AI Training Datasets & Article 14 GDPR: A Risk Assessment for the Proportionality Exemption of the Obligation to Provide Information." *Law, State and Telecommunications Review* 13 (2): 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.26512/lstr.v13i2.36253>.

The GDPR offers only minimal guidance on the format for communicating information to data subjects. "Form" refers to the organisation, structure, and presentation of the information. The GDPR suggests a few options, stating that information should be provided in writing or through other means, such as icons, and electronically when appropriate. Considering the growing volume of data processed online, electronic formats should be prioritised. One specific example mentioned in the GDPR is the use of a website (Recital 58). Recital 60 mentions the possibility of utilising visual aids, such as standardised machine-readable icons to enhance the effectiveness of communication with data subjects, without expressly mandating the use of such tools by controllers. Additionally, under Article 14, the GDPR affords some discretion to controllers in regard to the timing for informing data subjects about the intended processing. When personal data is collected directly from the data subject, the information must be provided at the time of data collection (Article 13(1)). However, if the data is obtained from a third party, the controller must ensure the data subject receives the information either before the data is shared with a recipient (Article 14(3)) or at the time of the first communication if the primary purpose of processing is to communicate with the data subject (Article 14(2)). In other cases, the data subject must be informed within a reasonable timeframe, which should not exceed one month (Article 14(1)).

The transparency guidelines issued by Article 29 Working Party (WP29)⁵¹, and subsequently endorsed by the EDPB, emphasise that controllers will need to decide on the practical implementation aspects of Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR based on factors such as the nature of the intended processing and the implications for the data subjects.⁵²

Arguably, the most consequential difference between Articles 13 and 14 in relation to data processing for scientific research purposes involving data sharing among controllers, concerns the conditions under which a controller is exempt from disclosure requirements. The GDPR's provisions on exemptions aim to strike a balance between the legitimate interests of data controllers and the protection of data subjects. One of the most evident exemptions to the obligation to provide information occurs when the data subject already possesses all the information they are entitled to (Article 13(4)). In such instances, providing the information again is unnecessary and inefficient.

In case of data not being obtained directly from a data subject, the GDPR offers some further exceptions. First, the information duty is limited if it proves impossible or would require disproportionate effort, especially when data is used for archiving in the public interest, for scientific or historical research purposes, or statistical reasons (Article 14(5)(b)). The lack of a corresponding provision in Article 13 has been understood to imply that the limitation on disclosure obligations due to impossibility or disproportionate effort applies solely to controllers who acquire personal data from

⁵¹ The European Data Protection Board replaced the Article 29 Working Party (WP29), established by Directive 95/46/EC and that dealt with issues relating to the protection of privacy and personal data until 25 May 2018 (entry into application of the GDPR).

⁵² Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. "Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679." WP260rev.01. <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/622227/en>.

sources other than the data subject (i.e., ‘downstream controllers’).⁵³ This distinction is also clearly emphasised in the WP29 Guidance on Transparency, which states that, in the context of Art. 14(5)(b) of the GDPR, “impossibility or disproportionate effort only arise by virtue of circumstances which do not apply if the personal data is collected from the data subject. In other words, the impossibility or disproportionate effort must be directly connected to the fact that the personal data was obtained other than from the data subject.”⁵⁴

However, interpreting open-ended terms like "disproportionate" can be difficult in certain cases. Any downstream controller wishing to invoke this exemption for processing personal data for scientific research must demonstrate that informing data subjects about the intended processing would indeed be impossible or involve disproportionate effort. This exemption must meet the proportionality test, meaning it must respect the essence of fundamental rights and be necessary and proportionate in a democratic society. The balancing test involves weighing the effort required by the data controller to provide information against the impact on the data subject if they are not informed.⁵⁵ In this assessment, the controller must consider factors such as the number of data subjects, the age of the data, and any safeguards adopted by the controller (Recital 62, GDPR). If this balancing exercise leads the downstream controller to conclude that informing individual data subjects would be a disproportionate effort, the controller may rely on the exemption under Article 14(5)(b), provided that the processing is for scientific research purposes and is conducted with appropriate safeguards in accordance with Article 89(1). Nonetheless, the controller remains responsible for making information about the processing publicly available. This can be achieved, for instance, by publishing the information on the controller’s website, which demonstrates compliance with the transparency principle.

There is significant uncertainty about when a controller must proactively inform data subjects about the processing of previously collected data. A clear exception is further processing, where the controller must notify the data subject if the data is used for a new purpose (Arts. 13(3) and 14(4) GDPR). The GDPR is less specific about other situations that require notification. The WP29 suggests that any significant changes to data processing that affect data subjects’ rights should be communicated transparently and fairly, allowing data subjects to opt out. This includes changes like transferring data to a new controller or identifying a new legal basis under Art. 6(1) of the GDPR, even when the data is processed strictly for the purpose(s) that motivated the initial data collection, namely when no further processing is taking place. However, it is unclear if more technical changes, such as new encryption methods, need to be communicated. WP29 also notes that controllers should periodically remind data subjects about ongoing data processing to ensure they remain informed. Ultimately, the controller must assess the need for notifications based on transparency and fairness

⁵³ Erdos, David. 2021. “Identification in EU Data Protection Law.” SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3761068>.

⁵⁴ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. “Guidelines on Transparency under Regulation 2016/679.” WP260rev.01. <https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/article29/items/622227/en>.

⁵⁵ *ibid*

principles, except in clear cases of information duty/disclosure obligation like further processing or data transfer.

Despite the legal uncertainties mentioned earlier, some general conclusions can be drawn about controllers' disclosure obligations under Articles 13 and 14 of the GDPR. Firstly, downstream controllers who receive existing data from other controllers generally have more exemptions from mandatory disclosure obligations compared to initial controllers who collect data directly from data subjects. Secondly, the initial controller must inform data subjects when they:

- i) Intend to further process the data for a purpose different from the one for which it was originally collected;
- ii) Plan to make changes to the processing that significantly impact data subjects' rights, including which rights apply and how they can be exercised;
- iii) Find it necessary to remind data subjects about the nature of the ongoing processing to ensure they remain adequately informed.

It is significant that the mandatory disclosure obligations affect Can.Heal cohorts, who are the parties responsible for samples and data collection from patients and research participants, making them data controllers subject to Art. 13 of the GDPR. By contrast, external researchers who intend to use existing sample and data collections for a new research project would qualify as downstream controllers subject to Art. 14, including its wider range of possible exemptions under Art.14(5)(b).

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) Data subjects' rights are a good example of "data protection by design and default." One should think first about how they are to be exercised (e.g., information portal, information notice, information provided in the consent form).**
- 2) Controller should inform about the processing in time, completely and for each purpose. The information provided should be based on an assessment of how people will be able to learn about the (further) use of their data. Just publishing on the website might not be enough. Controller is responsible for proving that a data subject received required information.**
- 3) Providing transparent and complete information is the only way to gain and maintain trust.**
- 4) The information duty is limited when data not being obtained directly from the data subject, especially when data subject already has the information or when performing scientific research and information of the data subjects proves impossible or would involve a disproportionate effort.**

The Right of Access and the Right to Data Portability

The right of access to personal data applies after data processing begins, unlike the right to information, which is crucial also before that the processing starts. Having access to information that is processed by data controllers tends to meet two objectives: (1) protecting the right to privacy and (2) establishing a level playing field between data subjects and controllers.⁵⁶ Informational rights (Articles 13 and 14), right of access (Art. 15 GDPR) and the right to data portability (Art. 20 GDPR) are crucial control entitlements that significantly enhance users' ability to manage their personal data.

The right of access outlined in Article 15 can be divided into several entitlements:

1. It gives the data subject the right to know whether their personal data is being processed.
2. It provides the data subject with the right to be informed about the nature of the data processing. This additional information must be presented in a clear and understandable manner and should include details such as the purposes of processing, the categories of data involved, the recipients or categories of recipients who receive the data, the retention period, the data subject's other rights (including the right to file a complaint with a supervisory authority), the source of the data if it was not collected directly from the data subject, and information regarding the existence and specifics of automated decision-making processes.
3. It grants data subjects access to the entirety of the data being processed by the controller, allowing them to obtain a copy of the data being processed (Article 15(3)). The Article further specifies that where requests to access data are made electronically, the data should be provided in an electronic form that is commonly used.

In its interpretive guidance on the right of access, the EDPB highlights that the format and medium of communication should be tailored to the specific request. In cases involving large amounts of data, the EDPB advises providing the information in a structured and layered format to enhance clarity.⁵⁷ The EDPB also emphasizes that data controllers must fulfil access requests in a way that does not infringe on the rights of others. For instance, when responding to an access request, the controller must assess whether the data to provide includes personal information about another data subject (for ethical considerations of genomic data of relatives, please see deliverable 12.2.). However, the controller cannot refuse the requesting data subject access solely because the data includes another individual's personal data. Instead, the controller should seek ways to comply with the request while balancing the rights of all parties involved. One possible solution is to provide a redacted version of the data with information about the other data subject removed.

⁵⁶ Vrabec, H. U. (2021). *Data subject rights under the GDPR: With a commentary through the lens of the data-driven economy*. Oxford University Press.

⁵⁷ European Data Protection Board. 2022. "Guidelines 01/2022 on data subject rights - Right of access" 1/2022. https://www.edpb.europa.eu/system/files/2023-04/edpb_guidelines_202201_data_subject_rights_access_v2_en.pdf

The EDPB acknowledges that fulfilling access requests may impose costs or administrative burdens on the controller. Nevertheless, the EDPB clarifies that controllers must be prepared to comply with access requests, including providing a complete copy of the data subject's personal data being processed, free of charge. In certain circumstances, controllers may charge a reasonable fee for access, but only if they can demonstrate that the request is "manifestly unfounded or excessive" or if the data subject requests multiple copies of the data. However, the EDPB explicitly states that the first copy must be provided free of charge, even if reproduction costs are high. Before charging a reasonable fee, controllers should provide an indication of their plan to do so to the data subjects. The latter must be enabled to decide whether they will withdraw the request to avoid being charged.

The right to obtain a copy of personal data under Article 15 of the GDPR bears some resemblance to the right to data portability under Article 20. While data portability enables the data subject not only to receive a copy for personal use but also to transfer the data to another processing system in a commonly used electronic format, control over these rights can be restricted in certain circumstances, such as national security concerns or other significant justifications (Article 23). Additionally, some rights may be subject to inherent limitations. For instance, the right to data portability applies only when the data is processed through automated means and based on an individual's consent (Article 6(1)(a), together with Article 9(2)(a) for special categories of data) or on the performance of a contract (Article 6(1)(b)). **When data is processed based on other legal basis than consent or contract (e.g. public interest), the right to data portability will not apply.**

The right to access and data portability intend to empower data subjects by giving them greater control over their personal data. Recital 68 underscores this objective by stating that to further reinforce control over their own data, data subjects should have the ability to receive the personal data they have provided to a controller in a structured, commonly used, machine-readable, and interoperable format, and transfer it to another controller, provided the processing is carried out by automated means. To effectively control data processing, portability will have to be enforced together with the right to erasure so that data (and not a copy of the data) move from one controller to another. Only when merged with the right to erasure does data portability enable full control over the processing of a data subject's personal data. However, in the healthcare sector, the implementation of the right to data portability has been hindered by the lack of interoperability standards. Similarly, Article 20 is silent about the specific control-enhancing functions of the right to data portability, which can be distilled only from the whole text of the GDPR.

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) In the context of Can.Heal, the right to data portability could be exercised by a data subject only when the data is processed through automated means and based on an individual's consent.**
- 2) The right to data portability only applies under the condition that the data subject has directly provided the data to the controller.**

Right to Rectification, Erasure, Restriction of Processing, and the Right to Object

The Right to Rectification allows individuals to have inaccurate personal data corrected or incomplete data completed. Given that genomic data is highly specific and scientifically precise, errors in the recording or interpretation of genetic information could have serious consequences, including misdiagnosis or inappropriate treatment. In genomic data, rectification might be more complex because genetic data itself (DNA sequences) cannot be "wrong" or "inaccurate" per se, but the associated data (e.g., family history, clinical findings) could be. Correcting such data could be requested, but correcting or altering the actual genetic data would be impossible in most cases, as DNA sequences reflect a biological truth. For instance, a data subject may have the right to correct contact information or other operational data, but not biomedical data generated through research analysis. This is particularly relevant when the controller needs to retain unaltered data to ensure study reproducibility or to maintain consistency in data analysis, ensuring that future analyses use the same data set. Article 16 of the GDPR is the expression of the data subjects' power to control (the quality of) their data. The right to rectification is intrinsically linked to the right of access: once data subjects have accessed their personal information and discovered that it is inaccurate or incomplete with regard to the purpose of the processing, they have the correlated right to have the data rectified or completed. The importance of this right to have the rectifications forwarded is shown by the fact that it allows the data subject to stop or at least limit the spreading of false information. The purposes of the processing must be taken into consideration when interpreting the right to rectification. In research contexts, this right may need to be more narrowly defined, allowing the controller to limit its application when appropriate based on the processing objectives. The GDPR lays down additional rights aimed at enabling the data subject to exercise a degree of control over how their data are processed, following initial data collection. However, there is considerable uncertainty as to the scope of the right. In particular, it has been noted that there is a tendency to conflate data accuracy with the broader notion of data quality.⁵⁸

The right to erasure, popularly known as the right to be forgotten, allows data subjects to seek the deletion of data and block further reuse when consent is withdrawn or when the data is no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which it was collected or otherwise processed (Art 17. GDPR). It is commonly conceptualised in the biomedical research discourse as a research participant's right to have their personal data removed through, for example, withdrawing their consent to study participation. Importantly, the right to erasure is not limited to the situations where personal data are processed based on the Art. 6(1)(a) of the GDPR's legal basis. It may also apply to processing under Articles 6(1)(f) and 6(1)(e), albeit here, the right to erasure is contingent on the applicability of the right to object (Art. 21) and must be preceded by the data subject's expressed objection to processing in accordance with Art. 21(1). This means that genomic data may not always be subject to full erasure if it is being used for long-term research that benefits the public.

⁵⁸ Dimitrova, Diana. 2021. "The Rise of the Personal Data Quality Principle. Is It Legal and Does It Have an Impact on the Right to Rectification?" SSRN Electronic Journal. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3790602>.

As a tool of control, the right to erasure aligns with the active aspect of privacy, commonly referred to as “privacy as control,” and specifically relates to the right to data protection. It implies that individuals have the primary authority to regulate the dissemination and use of information about themselves. However, this control faces practical limitations in the context of scientific research. For instance, it may not be feasible to remove data retroactively from analyses already completed. Additionally, retaining personal data may be necessary to ensure the reproducibility of research.⁵⁹ These considerations are also reflected in the GDPR, with Article 17(3)(d) providing a built-in limitation on this right when data processing is conducted for scientific research purposes in accordance with Article 89(1).

The right to restriction of processing under Article 18 complements the right to erasure (Article 17) by giving individuals the ability to limit the processing of their personal data without requiring its deletion. This right is particularly important in situations where:

- a) The processing is unlawful but the data subject does not want their data to be deleted. This could occur when the individual prefers the data to remain but wishes to halt further processing (e.g. while disputing how their genomic data was processed or determining if consent was given correctly).
- b) The data is no longer needed for its original purpose, but the data subject still needs the data to pursue legal claims, defend themselves, or exercise their legal rights.

Unlike the right to erasure, which has specific restrictions for scientific research under Article 17(3)(d), the right to restriction of processing does not have automatic exemptions for research. This means that in most cases, the right to restrict data processing would still apply to research data unless a specific national law limits this right under Article 89(2) of the GDPR. Such derogations would allow scientific research to continue despite a request for restriction, provided that the national law deems it necessary for research purposes.

The right to object in Article 21 applies specifically where the processing is based on the legal grounds of Article 6(1)(e) (tasks carried out in the public interest) or Article 6(1)(f) (legitimate interests). When a data subject exercises their right to object, the controller has three choices:

- a) To cease the processing: The controller can comply with the request and stop processing the data.
- b) To demonstrate legitimate grounds: The controller can continue processing if they can prove that their legitimate reasons for processing outweigh the individual's interests, rights, and freedoms.

⁵⁹ Peloquin, David, Michael DiMaio, Barbara Bierer, and Mark Barnes. 2020. “Disruptive and Avoidable: GDPR Challenges to Secondary Research Uses of Data.” *European Journal of Human Genetics* 28 (6): 697–705. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-020-0596-x>.

- c) To make legal claims: The controller can also argue that continued processing is necessary for establishing, exercising, or defending legal claims.

The right to object applies to data processing for scientific research under Article 21(6) but with an important limitation. If the processing is necessary for a task carried out in the public interest, such as certain scientific research projects, the objection may not be upheld. Similarly to the right to restriction, any limitations on the right to object in the context of research can only be made through national law derogations based on Article 89(2).

In summary, while both the right to restriction of processing and the right to object provide strong protections for individuals' control over their data, scientific research is treated as a special case under the GDPR. National laws can create exemptions for research activities, particularly when deemed in the public interest, allowing data processing to continue despite these rights.

Derogations from Data Subjects' Rights under National Laws of a Member State

Article 89(2) of the GDPR provides grounds for Member States to adopt national laws derogating from certain data subject rights where processing takes place for scientific research purposes. Derogations from data subjects' rights are not available to all controllers. The derogations only apply if, and to the extent that, the Member State in which a controller is based has implemented a law derogating from data subjects' rights. Article 89(2) explicitly mentions derogations from only a subset of rights. Namely, it lists the following Articles that can be derogated from based on national laws: Art. 15 (the right of access), Art. 16 (the right to rectification), Art. 18 (the right to restriction of processing), and Art. 21 (the right to object). Article 89(2) does not refer to other rights of data subjects, which can be interpreted as the legislator's intention to exclude some of the rights from the scope of derogations. However, this appears incongruous with Recital 156 of the GDPR, which provides a more comprehensive list of data subject rights that can be derogated by national laws governing scientific research.⁶⁰

Furthermore, some uncertainty is introduced by Art. 23, which states that data subjects' rights can be restricted based on a Union or national law, while Art. 23 concerns all the rights of data subjects under Chapter III of the GDPR. According to Art. 23(1), one of the aims of a Union or national law restricting data subjects' rights may be to safeguard "important objectives of general public interest" (Art. 23(1)(e)). However, the Article does not explicitly include scientific research as part of these objectives. This has created uncertainties around the legislator's intention to differentiate processing falling under this Article from processing carried out in public interest within the meaning of Art. 6(1)(e), where the latter may include scientific research. Should "important objectives of general

⁶⁰ Shabani, Mahsa, and Pascal Borry. 2018. "Rules for Processing Genetic Data for Research Purposes in View of the New EU General Data Protection Regulation." *European Journal of Human Genetics* 26 (2): 149–56. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41431-017-0045-7>.

public interest” be interpreted in a manner that includes scientific research, it might be possible to adopt laws governing research that derogate from the data subjects’ rights beyond those referred to in Article 89(2). On the other hand, a narrower interpretation would mean that only the rights explicitly listed in Article 89(2) can be derogated from.⁶¹

Of note, even among the countries whose national laws make use of the Art. 89(2) GDPR prerogative, the extent to which the relevant data subjects’ rights are derogated may be different. One example of this is Norway, where the Art. 89(2) GDPR prerogative has been implemented in a manner that derogates from some, but not all the rights mentioned in Art. 89(2).⁶² Such differences across countries, once again, highlight the importance of understanding subtle yet consequential ways in which the diverging national implementations of the GDPR may affect various aspects of data processing in a cross-border context.

Implications for Controllers’ Obligations vis-a-vis Data Subjects

Where personal data are processed in complex environments involving multiple controllers as it may be in the Can.Heal project, there are important differences in the GDPR compliance obligations of the different controllers vis-a-vis data subjects. These obligations appear to disproportionately fall on the initial controller, that is, the party that collected personal data directly from the data subject. There are generally fewer exemptions or derogations from data subjects’ rights available to the initial controller, compared to downstream controllers who do not collect personal data directly from the data subjects. For example, mandatory informational disclosure requirements under Art. 13 GDPR appear to always apply in principle, which implies that the initial controller will generally have the obligation to recontact data subjects prior to introducing material changes to data processing, and/or provide periodic notifications concerning ongoing processing. This could be problematic in the context of scientific research, given that recontacting research participants is widely considered administratively burdensome and is often perceived as a significant practical barrier to continued research use of personal data.⁶³ Furthermore, it is unclear to what extent Union or national laws can derogate from Art. 13 obligations. On the other hand, downstream controllers who process personal data for research purposes can rely on several potential exemptions from disclosure obligations, under Art. 14(5)(b).

⁶¹ Mourby, Mirand, Heather Gowans, Stergios Aidinlis, Hannah Smith, and Jane Kaye. 2019. “Governance of Academic Research Data under the GDPR—Lessons from the UK.” *International Data Privacy Law* 9 (3): 192–206. <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipz010>.

⁶² Befring, Anne Kjersti. 2021. “Norwegian Biobanks: Increased Complexity with GDPR and National Law.” In *GDPR and Biobanking: Individual Rights, Public Interest and Research Regulation across Europe*, edited by Santa Slokenberga, Olga Tzortzatou, and Jane Reichel, 323–44. Law, Governance and Technology Series. Cham: Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-49388-2_18.

⁶³ Mitchell, Colin, Corrette Ploem, Valesca Retèl, Sjeff Gevers, and Raoul Hennekam. 2020. “Experts Reflecting on the Duty to Recontact Patients and Research Participants; Why Professionals Should Take the Lead in Developing Guidelines.” *European Journal of Medical Genetics* 63 (2): 103642. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejmg.2019.03.006>.

In complex data processing environments, the initial controller is also generally responsible for supporting data subjects in exercising their rights with respect to other controllers (Art. 19 GDPR). When a data subject contacts the initial controller with a request to exercise their rights, particularly the rights under Articles 16 (right to rectification), 17 (right to erasure), and 18 (right to restriction of processing) of the GDPR, **the initial controller is required to notify all recipients of data subject’s personal data, including downstream controllers.** The obligation to notify data recipients applies unless compliance is “impossible or involves disproportionate effort” (Art. 19 GDPR). A common interpretation of the Article 19 obligation, at least in the context of biobanking, is that the controller is required to notify those recipients with whom the controller has directly disclosed the data, whereas notification of any subsequent recipients amounts to disproportionate effort.⁶⁴ It is important to emphasise further that **in practice, support from the initial controller is necessary for exercising data subject rights** that are not explicitly mentioned in Art. 19 GDPR. Downstream controllers may have no means to authenticate the identity of the data subject; Art. 11 GDPR expressly states that controllers are not required to store information needed for re-identifying data subjects for the sole purpose of complying with data subjects’ potential future requests under Articles 15-20 GDPR. Because scientific research commonly relies on robustly pseudonymised data, downstream controllers are unlikely to collect the information required to authenticate data subjects’ identities. Consequently, the involvement of the initial controller will probably be necessary to enable the exercise of all rights of the data subject.

Recommendations for the Can.Heal stakeholders:

- 1) The exercise of the right to rectification, erasure, restriction of processing, and the right to object are limited and vary based on the legal basis, purposes of the processing and national legislation.**
- 2) The initial controller is generally responsible for supporting the data subjects in exercising their rights with respect to other controllers. The initial controller is required to notify all recipients of data subject’s personal data, including downstream controllers.**

⁶⁴ Staunton, Ciara. 2021. “Individual Rights in Biobank Research Under the GDPR.” In *GDPR and Biobanking: Individual Rights, Public Interest and Research Regulation across Europe*, 43:91–104. Law, Governance and Technology Series. Springer.

Chapter 3: Lawfulness of Genomic Data Sharing in Can.Heal

The lawfulness of genomic data sharing refers to the legal framework and conditions under which genomic data can be collected, processed, shared, and used in compliance with applicable laws and regulations. In genomic data sharing the most relevant parties are:⁶⁵

- 1) Data providers (controllers or joint controllers).
- 2) Platform, resp. entity legally responsible for it (processor for most of the processing activities).
- 3) Data users (controllers or joint controllers).

This chapter introduces two inextricably connected notions without which no processing of personal data can take place: **legal basis** for the processing and **purpose** of the processing. EDPB states in their Guidelines 4/2019 in paragraph 68 that “the appropriate legal basis must be clearly connected to the specific purpose of processing.”⁶⁶

A legal basis under the GDPR refers to the justification required for processing personal data. Each legal basis must be appropriately linked to the specific purpose of the data processing to ensure compliance with the GDPR. The list of legal grounds must be understood as exhaustive and final. As far as Member States’ legislators are at all allowed to act under Article 6(1), all legislative activities must keep within the strict boundaries it sets. There is no ranking between Article 6(1)(a)– (f) in the sense that one ground has normative priority over the others.

Each of the legal basis must be accompanied with a valid purpose of a processing (e.g. when controller relies on consent as a legal basis, the consent for the processing must be given for a specific purpose; when controller wants to or is obliged to process personal data based on a law, it is the law that provides purpose for the envisaged processing.

Purpose

Purpose specification is crucial for a controller’s GDPR compliance, as it is integral to multiple data protection principles, particularly the principle of purpose limitation outlined in Article 5(1) of the GDPR. This principle requires that personal data be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not processed in ways incompatible with those purposes. The process of purpose specification enables controllers to assess whether further data processing is permissible and compatible with the initial purpose, thereby ensuring compliance with GDPR.

⁶⁵ For more detailed information please see controller/ processor chapter and Secondary Use and Further Processing chapter

⁶⁶ The European Data Protection Board. Guidelines 4/2019 on Article 25 Data Protection by Design and by Default Version 2.0. https://edpb.europa.eu/sites/default/files/files/file1/edpb_guidelines_201904_dataprotection_by_design_and_by_default_v2.0_en.pdf.

Purpose specification also plays a significant role in ensuring compliance with other GDPR principles. For instance, it is closely linked to the principle of lawfulness, which requires that the legal basis for data processing be connected to the specific purpose. **In cases where consent is the legal basis, the purpose must be clearly defined;** otherwise, consent may become invalid, rendering the processing unlawful. Purpose specification further supports adherence to principles like transparency, data minimisation, storage limitation, and accuracy by guiding decisions on the types of data needed, the duration of processing, and the accuracy of data relative to its purposes.

Moreover, purpose specification is essential for fulfilling procedural and accountability obligations under the GDPR. Controllers must document the purposes of processing in their Records of Processing Activities (RoPA), as required by Article 30. Understanding the purposes of processing also aids in assigning GDPR roles and responsibilities in complex data processing environments, ensuring that all parties involved are aware of their obligations and potential liabilities.

Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR provides for the purpose limitation principle, which requires that personal data must be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with those purposes. The definition of a "purpose" under the GDPR is critical for several key aspects of data processing: identifying the data controller, determining the conditions for further processing, selecting the appropriate legal basis—particularly whether consent is suitable—ensuring transparency, and maintaining overall GDPR compliance. However, the GDPR does not directly define what constitutes a valid purpose.

There is considerable debate as to how narrowly the purpose(s) of data processing must be defined, particularly in the context of scientific research. This discussion stems from Recital 33 of the GDPR, which allows for consent “for certain areas of research” where it is not possible “to fully identify the purpose of personal data processing for scientific research purposes at the time of data collection”⁶⁷ This question is further elaborated in the chapter Lawfulness of Processing Genomic Data for Scientific Research and Policy development (p. 57).

These are the characteristics of a purpose:

1. **Specificity:** The purpose for processing data must be clearly defined (e.g., Art. 6(1)(a) / Art. 25(2) GDPR). Article 5(1)(b) GDPR emphasizes that the purpose should be specifically articulated to ensure that processing activities are necessary for achieving that purpose. This specificity is crucial for demonstrating GDPR compliance in areas such as transparency, lawful processing, and data minimisation.

⁶⁷ Verhenneman, G., K. Claes, J. J. Derèze, P. Herijgers, C. Mathieu, F. E. Rademakers, R. Reyda, and M. Vanautgaerden. 2020. “How GDPR Enhances Transparency and Fosters Pseudonymisation in Academic Medical Research.” *European Journal of Health Law* 27 (1): 35–57. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-12251009>.

2. **Defined duration of processing:** The purpose must provide a clear framework for determining how long the data will be processed (Art. 5(1)(e), Art. 25(2), Art. 13(2)/14(2) GDPR). This implies that a valid purpose should not result in indefinite data processing with no clear outcome. Instead, clear criteria should be established to evaluate when the purpose has been achieved, thereby providing an endpoint to the processing. The French term for purpose, *finalité*, which suggests an "end" or "outcome," reinforces this idea that purposes must have a defined goal.
3. **Relationship between purpose and data:** While a purpose does not have to explicitly define data subjects, data types, or recipients (Art. 4(7) GDPR), it must be specific enough to determine these elements before processing begins (Art. 13(1), Art. 14(1) GDPR). The controller must demonstrate that the data to be processed are necessary for achieving the stated purpose (Art. 5(1)(c), Art. 25(2), Art. 35(7)(b) GDPR). This connection between purpose and data serves as a safeguard against excessive or irrelevant data collection.
4. **Timing of purpose specification:** The purpose for processing must be established at the time of data collection (Art. 5(1)(b) GDPR) or, in cases of further processing, before that processing begins (Art. 13(3), Art. 14(4) GDPR). This ensures that processing activities are aligned with the stated purpose from the outset and helps maintain transparency and data subject rights.

Drawing from these principles and EDPB guidelines, we conclude that a purpose must be sufficiently specific to guide the design of processing activities—clarifying what processing is included or excluded—and to justify the collection of specific data types and the selection of data subjects. Furthermore, the purpose should aim at achieving a concrete outcome or goal consistent with the concept of *finalité*.

Suitable Legal Bases for Genomic Data Sharing

The choice of legal basis is important because different rights, or exceptions to them, flow from each choice of legal basis. The controller is responsible for proving that each processing operation has a legitimate legal basis and, in the case of special category personal data, a valid exemption under Article 9(2). Crucially, the legitimacy of a GDPR legal basis must be evaluated considering the following factors: the nature and context of the processing, the specific purpose(s) for which the processing is undertaken, as well as the controller's identity, legal structure, and jurisdiction of establishment. Personal data shall only be processed if one of six legal bases can be satisfied (Article 6(1)). These are (the most relevant ones for genomic data sharing in bold):

- a) **the data subject has given consent to the processing of his or her personal data for one or more specific purposes;**
- b) processing is necessary for the performance of a contract to which the data subject is party or in order to take steps at the request of the data subject prior to entering into a contract;

- c) **processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject;**
- d) **processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person;**
- e) **processing is necessary for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest or in the exercise of official authority vested in the controller;**
- f) **processing is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate interests pursued by the controller or by a third party, except where such interests are overridden by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject which require protection of personal data, in particular where the data subject is a child.**

Even when a legal basis for processing personal data has been established, the processing of special categories of data (e.g. genetic data, health-related data, biometric data) is still prohibited under Article 9(1) of the GDPR unless one of the ten conditions outlined in Article 9(2) applies. These conditions (exemptions) are as follows (the most relevant exemptions for genomic data sharing in bold):

- a) **the data subject has given explicit consent to the processing of those personal data for one or more specified purposes, except where Union or Member State law provide that the prohibition referred to in paragraph 1 may not be lifted by the data subject;**
- b) processing is necessary for the purposes of carrying out the obligations and exercising specific rights of the controller or of the data subject in the field of employment and social security and social protection law in so far as it is authorised by Union or Member State law or a collective agreement pursuant to Member State law providing for appropriate safeguards for the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject;
- c) processing is necessary to protect the vital interests of the data subject or of another natural person where the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent;
- d) processing is carried out in the course of its legitimate activities with appropriate safeguards by a foundation, association or any other not-for-profit body with a political, philosophical, religious or trade union aim and on condition that the processing relates solely to the members or to former members of the body or to persons who have regular contact with it in connection with its purposes and that the personal data are not disclosed outside that body without the consent of the data subjects;
- e) **processing relates to personal data which are manifestly made public by the data subject;**
- f) processing is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims or whenever courts are acting in their judicial capacity;
- g) **processing is necessary for reasons of substantial public interest, on the basis of Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the**

essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject;

- h) processing is necessary for the purposes of preventive or occupational medicine, for the assessment of the working capacity of the employee, medical diagnosis, the provision of health or social care or treatment or the management of health or social care systems and services on the basis of Union or Member State law or pursuant to contract with a health professional and subject to the conditions and safeguards;**
- i) processing is necessary for reasons of public interest in the area of public health, such as protecting against serious cross-border threats to health or ensuring high standards of quality and safety of health care and of medicinal products or medical devices, on the basis of Union or Member State law which provides for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the rights and freedoms of the data subject, in particular professional secrecy;**
- j) processing is necessary for archiving purposes in the public interest, scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes in accordance with Article 89(1) based on Union or Member State law which shall be proportionate to the aim pursued, respect the essence of the right to data protection and provide for suitable and specific measures to safeguard the fundamental rights and the interests of the data subject.**

Legal basis is a critically important concept for compliance reasons. A missing or insufficient legal basis is the single most frequently cited violation in GDPR fines issued by supervisory authorities.⁶⁸ Irrespective of how a data reuse lifecycle is structured, every processing operation carried out on the personal data must have defined:

1. the purpose(s) for which the processing is performed;
2. the data controller(s) for the processing; and
3. a valid GDPR legal basis in which the processing is grounded.

Consent

The first and foremost frequently used legal basis is a consent. Article 4(11) of the GDPR defines the “consent” of the data subject as any freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of the data subject’s wishes by which he or she, by a statement or by a clear affirmative action signifies agreement to the processing of personal data relating to him or her. Consent as a legal basis in the GDPR has been designed to give data subjects the greatest extent of control over their data and, also

⁶⁸ Saemann, M., and others, ‘Investigating GDPR Fines in the Light of Data Flows’ (2022) 2022 Proceedings on Privacy Enhancing Technologies 314.

imposes rather strict obligations to the controllers they must adhere to be compliant. Consent is a legal basis for processing based on Article 6(1) and represents one of the exemptions from the general prohibition of processing special categories of personal data listed in Article 9(2). It is, therefore, possible to use one consent containing combined qualitative criteria required in both articles. Whenever referred to a “consent” for genomic data processing, it is typically Art. 6(1)(a) GDPR, in conjunction with Art. 9(2)(a) GDPR. The EDPB also considers it appropriate to rely on the Art. 6(1)(a) legal basis and the Art. 9(2)(a) condition in conjunction.

Using consent as a legal basis for processing personal data under the GDPR has several important implications, including specificity and clarity, validity, revocability and granularity, documentation, age considerations, transparency, and fairness.

1. Specificity and clarity

Consent for processing genomic data must be obtained for specific⁶⁹ and specified⁷⁰ purposes. This means that the data subject must be clearly informed about the purposes for which their data will be used. Valid consent can only be given for an individual purpose and not for bundled and/or vaguely described purposes (recital 32: “[...] *When the processing has multiple purposes, consent should be given for all of them.*”). Article 9(2)(a) adds an additional requirement of being “specified” to the already specific purpose. This represents a higher threshold than being “just” specific and requires a high degree of precision and definiteness in the declaration of consent, as well as a precise description of the purposes of processing.⁷¹

2. Informed consent and its validity

The data subject must be fully informed about the nature of the data processing, including the purposes, the data controller’s identity, and their rights. This ensures that consent is given freely and with full knowledge of the implications. Under the GDPR, consent is presumed not to be freely given and therefore invalid when there is a clear power imbalance between the data subject and the controller. This is often the case in healthcare and research, particularly when the controller is a public authority, as highlighted in Recital 43. The EDPB warns that power imbalances are likely when participants are unwell or belong to disadvantaged groups, suggesting that consent may be an unsuitable legal basis for much health research. However, others argue that Recital 43 calls for consideration of specific circumstances, indicating that a power imbalance may not exist in certain genomics research.⁷² This should also be read in light of recital 42 that for consent to be informed, in keeping with the definition of Article 4(11) GDPR, **the controller needs to be known to the data**

⁶⁹ Article 6(1)(a) of the GDPR

⁷⁰ Article 9(2)(a) of the GDPR

⁷¹ Georgieva, in Kuner, Bygrave, Docksey, The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary, Article 9 GDPR, p. 365 (Oxford University Press 2020).

⁷² Hallinan D. Broad consent under the GDPR: An optimistic perspective on a bright future. Life Sciences, Society, and Policy. 2020; 16(1): 1-18.

subject. The EDPB does not entirely rule out consent but advises a thorough assessment of circumstances before using it as a legal basis.

Consent under the GDPR for processing personal data should not be confused with informed consent given by patients or research participants in medical studies. While both require transparency, clear information, and voluntary agreement, they differ significantly. Informed consent for research is a standard practice and often legally required for certain biomedical studies, independent of GDPR. While informed consent typically covers all aspects of study participation (including any associated medical procedure, collection and research use of samples and data), consent within the meaning of GDPR only concerns the processing of personal data.

3. Revocability and granularity

Consent can be withdrawn at any time. The data subject must be informed of their right to withdraw consent and the process for doing so. Once consent is withdrawn, the data controller must stop processing the data unless another legal basis applies. However, once data are disclosed, the consent cannot be withdrawn retroactively because the consent had been valid until it was withdrawn. Consent must be granular, meaning that it should be obtained separately for different processing activities. Blanket consent for multiple purposes is not acceptable. Consent for disclosing and processing personal data for reuse or downstream research projects becomes more complex. Each time data is accessed for e.g. research project, it constitutes a distinct purpose requiring specific consent under GDPR. According to Articles 6(1)(a) and 7, and supported by recitals 32 and 42, separate consent is needed for each data disclosure for a new research purpose. This interpretation has led to the development of dynamic consent solutions, where individuals must give consent for each reuse of their data. Dynamic consent, supported by digital tools, is gaining popularity in countries like Italy and Malta to ensure GDPR compliance.⁷³

4. Documentation

The data controller must be able to demonstrate that consent was obtained. This requires maintaining records of when, how, and for what purposes consent was given. Article 7(1) requires that when processing is based on consent, the controller must be able to prove that the data subject has consented to the processing of their personal data. In cases involving complex processing chains of health or genetic data with multiple controllers, each controller relying on consent as the legal basis must demonstrate that explicit consent was obtained from the data subject and is valid for the specific processing operations conducted by that controller. This should be understood in light of recital 42, which emphasizes that for consent to be informed, as defined in Article 4(11) GDPR, the controller must be identifiable to the data subject.

⁷³ Deborah Mascalzoni and others, 'Ten Years of Dynamic Consent in the CHRIS Study: Informed Consent as a Dynamic Process' (2022) 30 *European Journal of Human Genetics* 1391; Nicholas Mamo and others, 'Dwarna: A Blockchain Solution for Dynamic Consent in Biobanking' (2020) 28 *European Journal of Human Genetics* 609.

5. Age considerations

Parental consent is required for children under the age of 16 (or lower in some member states, but not below 13). This adds an additional layer of complexity when processing data from minors. As a child matures, the question arises of when to obtain direct consent for processing personal data, especially if consent was initially provided by a legal representative. According to the Art 29 Working Party's 2009 opinion, a child can revoke consent upon reaching adulthood or give explicit consent for continued data processing.⁷⁴ Genomic data controllers are encouraged to refresh consent as the child develops competence. Data controllers should develop strategies for seeking fresh consent from children once they are mature enough. Challenges include how to handle a competent minor's refusal of consent and managing the withdrawal of consent in contexts like genomic research, where removing data could weaken research or clash with obligations like recontacting participants.

6. Transparency and fairness

The data controller must ensure that the consent process is transparent and fair, providing clear and accessible information to the data subject.

For processing (regular) personal data or special category personal data, such as genetic and health data, the GDPR does not mandate an organisation to obtain the data subject's consent. Many in the health research community mistakenly believe that consent is the appropriate legal basis for the secondary use of health and genetic data. This confusion arises from conflating consent as a legal basis for data processing with the ethical requirement to obtain informed consent for research participation, a misconception known as the "consent misconception".⁷⁵ While informed consent is an ethical obligation, and sometimes a legal one, assuming that personal data processing is also based on consent under GDPR Article 6(1) is problematic.

Consent as a legal basis presents several conceptual and practical challenges, particularly when applied to secondary data use, such as in the case of "broad consent," which is referenced in GDPR recital 33. While consent is one possible legal basis for processing data, there are other valid grounds as well. The GDPR does not prioritize consent as the primary legal basis notably in the context of scientific research. Alternative and potentially more appropriate legal bases under GDPR Article 6 include legitimate interests (primarily relevant to commercial organisations) and tasks carried out in the public interest, provided that these are established by EU or Member State law applicable to the

⁷⁴ Article 29 Data Protection Working Party. Opinion 2/2009 on the protection of children's personal data (General Guidelines and the special case of schools). 2009.

⁷⁵ Edward S Dove and Jiahong Chen, 'Should Consent for Data Processing Be Privileged in Health Research? A Comparative Legal Analysis' (2020) 10 International Data Privacy Law 117; Eugenijus Gefenas and others, 'Controversies Between Regulations of Research Ethics and Protection of Personal Data: Informed Consent at a Cross-Road' (2022) 25 Medicine, Health Care and Philosophy 23.

controller. In light of this, several regulatory authorities advise researchers to rely on legal bases other than consent for processing personal data.⁷⁶

Legal Obligation

Another legal basis is a legal obligation. Some forms of processing of genetic/health data may be necessary for ‘compliance with a legal obligation’ (Art 6(1)(c)). This applies if the processing of personal data is a reasonable and proportionate way of complying with an obligation (Art 6(1)(c)) set forth in a law (processing is required by a Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject). Therefore, it is the law that provides the specified purpose. Article 6(1)(c) also applies in cases where the obligation is not fully defined in law but is established through an additional legal act under public law, such as secondary or delegated legislation, or even through a binding decision by a public authority in a specific case.

A Task Carried Out in the Public Interest

This provision is the general basis for the lawful processing of personal data for public sector purposes.⁷⁷ The European Data Protection Board suggests that Article 6(1)(e) GDPR, which allows data processing in the public interest, is a more appropriate legal basis for scientific research than the data subject’s consent (Article 6(1)(a) GDPR). It also offers advantages over legitimate interest (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR), particularly in reducing compliance burdens for data controllers and offering exemptions from some obligations. In biomedical research, Article 6(1)(e) is to be used in conjunction with Article 9(2)(j) GDPR, which governs the processing of special categories of data for scientific purposes. However, controllers can only rely on these articles if specific national or EU laws authorize them to process such data. Some countries lack the necessary laws, and even where they exist, they may only apply to certain institutions, such as public universities, excluding private entities. Thus, while GDPR Articles 6(1)(e) and 9(2)(j) are the best theoretical basis for research, their practical applicability depends on national regulations and the type of legal entity.

Legitimate Interest

A “legitimate interest” is an interest that is visibly recognised by law, although not necessarily explicitly, and more precisely by Union or Member State law. Particular relevance must be attributed to the fundamental rights and freedoms of a data subject as they are all potential sources of legitimate interests. Processing under Article 6(1)(f) is not permitted if the legitimate interests of the controller or a third party are outweighed by the interests or fundamental rights and freedoms of the data subject, especially when the data subject is a child. The mention of "interests or fundamental rights," without

⁷⁶ Health Research Authority, ‘GDPR Guidance,’ available at <https://www.hra.nhs.uk/planning-and-improving-research/policies-standards-legislation/data-protection-and-information-governance/gdpr-guidance/> last accessed 9.9.2024

⁷⁷ Kotschy, in Kuner, Bygrave, Docksey, *The EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR): A Commentary*, Article 6 GDPR, p. 335 (Oxford University Press 2020).

specifying that the interests must be "legitimate," provides broad protection to the data subject. Therefore, a controller wishing to rely on Article 6(1)(f) must carry out a specific "balancing test" in line with the principle of proportionality.

All processing for 'legitimate interests' is anyway limited to what is plausibly necessary to pursue this interest. In line with the principle of proportionality, processing can only be acknowledged as 'necessary' if no better-suited and less intrusive alternative is available. Demonstrating the necessity of the purpose for the task or mission assigned is crucial, in particular, where the initial controller who collected the data for its primary purpose, such as a specific research project, intends to make the data subsequently available for secondary use.

Lawfulness of Processing Genomic Data for Scientific Research and Policy development

The value of genetic and health data for purposes beyond research is increasingly recognised, especially for advancing scientific knowledge and supporting public health policies. Data sharing among research organizations enhances statistical power, promotes reproducibility, and avoids the need for further recruitment of participants, reducing participant fatigue. The broader biomedical research community is actively working on making existing data FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and establishing data-sharing platforms, including cross-border initiatives like the Cancer Image Europe and the European 1+ Million Genomes Initiative (1+MG). These initiatives are supported by European governments and align with the European Health Data Space Regulation, which aims to enable secondary use of health data for research, healthcare, and policy development. The GDPR and national laws in EU Member States form the legal framework for protecting personal data, particularly sensitive health and genetic data. This framework is complemented by sector-specific regulations, including healthcare laws, medical secrecy, and biomedical research rules, as well as relevant case law from the Court of Justice of the European Union.⁷⁸

The GDPR includes various exemptions and special conditions that provide favourable treatment to scientific research. These provisions are meant to allow for more flexibility in how personal data can be reused for research purposes. For instance, Article 5(1)(b) and Recital 50 of the GDPR state that the further processing of personal data for scientific research is considered lawful and compatible with the original purpose for which the data was collected, as long as it meets certain conditions. The GDPR also offers leniency regarding data subject consent in scientific research. Recital 33 allows for "broad consent," meaning individuals can give consent for general research areas without knowing specific future uses of their data. Moreover, Article 89(2) of the GDPR provides derogations from some data subject rights in the context of scientific research. This should allow researchers to bypass

⁷⁸ Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Edward S Dove, Legal bases for effective secondary use of health and genetic data in the EU: time for new legislative solutions to better harmonize data for cross-border sharing?, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2024;, ipae014, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae014>

certain obligations, such as responding to requests for data copies, rectifications, or erasures, which could be burdensome and interfere with research objectives. These derogations aim to balance the privacy rights of individuals with the societal benefits of advancing scientific research. However, these derogations for scientific research that are frequently mentioned in this document, do not always work as originally intended.

The definition of scientific research within the context of the GDPR is a subject of ongoing debate. In 2020, the European Data Protection Supervisor (EDPS) released a Preliminary Opinion on data protection in relation to scientific research. The EDPS emphasized that “genuine” research must align with the values and principles that govern the EU's scientific research framework. These principles include promoting the common good in the public interest, generating knowledge, and adhering to established safeguards like ethics reviews and scientific codes of conduct. The EDPS raised concerns that some non-academic, for-profit entities may improperly influence research outcomes to serve their interests, potentially disqualifying them from research exemptions. Moreover, even organizations explicitly dedicated to “genuine” research, such as public universities, may engage in data processing activities that fall outside the scope of scientific research. For example, using personal data for quality assurance purposes, which is not aimed at improving products or services, may not qualify as scientific research. In some European countries, national law explicitly distinguishes between scientific research and quality assurance activities. Even when further processing of personal data is clearly considered scientific research and deemed compatible under Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR, this does not automatically make the processing permissible.⁷⁹

Scientific research provides a foundation for policies grounded in objective, empirical data. Policymakers rely on research findings to craft solutions to social, economic, and other challenges. Research informs risk assessments and evaluates the potential impacts of different policy options. In sectors like public health, scientific research identifies risks associated with policy decisions and helps predict long-term outcomes. It also drives innovation, influencing policies that encourage technological advancements. In areas like medical research, biotechnology, or data privacy, scientific advancements often require new or updated policies. For instance, policies on genomic data privacy are developed based on research outcomes that reveal potential benefits or ethical concerns. Scientific research thus guides the creation of ethical and legal frameworks to govern emerging fields. In the context of data protection laws like the GDPR, scientific research informs how policies are developed to safeguard individuals’ privacy while enabling research to continue. In GDPR policy making does not have that explicit privileges as scientific research, however it is closely linked to it. In recital 156 and 157 the interrelatedness is clearly visible: “*On the basis of registries, research results can be enhanced, as they draw on a larger population. [...] Research results obtained through registries provide solid, high-quality knowledge which can provide the basis for the formulation and*

⁷⁹ Becker, R., Chokoshvili, D., Comandé, G., Dove, E. S., Hall, A., Mitchell, C., Molnár-Gábor, F., Nicolàs, P., Tervo, S., & Thorogood, A. (2022). Secondary Use of Personal Health Data: When Is It “Further Processing” Under the GDPR, and What Are the Implications for Data Controllers?. *European Journal of Health Law*, 30(2), 129-157. <https://doi.org/10.1163/15718093-bja10094>

implementation of knowledge-based policy, improve the quality of life for a number of people and improve the efficiency of social services.”

Consent

In the research community, there is a common misconception in conflating a consent for being involved in a research study with the GDPR consent as one of the legal bases for processing. Each one of these consents serves different purpose and whereas informed consent for biomedical research typically covers all aspects of study participation, GDPR consent is limited only to the processing of personal (genomic) data.

Consent for the genomic data processing must be given for well-defined individual (not bundled) purpose(s). Such purpose must be specific and specified. Regarding the "broad consent" seemingly allowed by Recital 33, a closer look at how the GDPR defines consent reveals that a one-time broad consent is not sufficient to serve as a valid legal basis for using data in future research projects. Under the GDPR, valid consent requires that the purpose and associated data processing be clearly specified. In the context of scientific research, this means that, at a minimum, the study's objectives, methodology, and, importantly, the identity of the organization conducting the study (i.e., the controller under the GDPR) must be known. Broad consent that appears to be enabled by recital 33 may be limited in scope to the primary purposes pursued by a particular controller when collecting the data, thus excluding any future secondary use.⁸⁰ This means that every controller who wants to rely on consent for further processing must obtain new consent from the data subject for future research projects once their specifics are identified. This may lead to consent fatigue and thus a high attrition rate and a bias in the available data.⁸¹

Future research-related activities that are undefined at the time of data collection inevitably lead to further processing, meaning the data will be used for a specific purpose that was not originally intended during the initial collection. This challenge—of not being able to identify all future purposes at the time of collection—is not unique to research and may also apply to other secondary uses. Consent for such further processing can be obtained upfront, but re-consenting would be required later, in line with the GDPR's principle that consent must be given for each specific purpose. The secondary use of existing personal data for research by the scientific community represents downstream processing, which does not influence how the data was originally collected. The decision to make data legally available for secondary research use can be a deliberate choice made by the initial data controller, who collects the data directly from the subjects.

⁸⁰ Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Edward S Dove, Legal bases for effective secondary use of health and genetic data in the EU: time for new legislative solutions to better harmonize data for cross-border sharing?, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2024;, ipae014, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae014>

⁸¹ Harriet JA Teare, Megan Pictor and Jane Kaye, 'Reflections on Dynamic Consent in Biomedical Research: The Story So Far' (2021) 29 *European Journal of Human Genetics* 649.

The "how" of processing, determined by the controller, refers to the technical, operational, and organizational aspects of the data access governance framework. The "what" pertains to the categories of permissible data reuses as known at the time of collection. Therefore, before making the data widely available, the controller must secure specific and informed consent from the data subject, covering these informational elements. The interpretation that each subsequent disclosure or reuse of data for a particular research project requires specific consent from the data subject has led to the creation of dynamic consent solutions, enabled by digital technology. In healthcare, purposes such as "informing the diagnosis of a similar patient" or "informing the therapy of a similar patient" might seem specific enough. However, upon closer inspection, variations may exist depending on the nature of the research question, the type of processing involved, and the specific data being consulted. A future data user cannot independently obtain consent for data reuse without the support of the initial controller or the data sharing intermediary that acts as the controller, since the data user lacks the means to re-contact the data subject (as per data subject rights).

Obtaining consent as the legal basis for processing health and genetic data is often impractical in the context of secondary data use. This conclusion contrasts with the widely held belief in the scientific research community that Recital 33 of the GDPR allows for broad consent at the time of data collection, which would remain valid for future processing without the need for renewed consent.

Consent for processing health and genetic data make it an impractical legal basis in the context of secondary data use lifecycle. This conclusion runs counter to the widely held view among the scientific research community that recital 33 permits a broad consent at the time of data collection, which remains valid for future further processing, that is, without the need to obtain a new consent. Also, data processed under consent as the GDPR legal basis cannot be readily reused by previously unspecified controllers, additional steps can be taken to enable lawful data sharing and reuse (re-consent). Nevertheless, consent remains a widely utilised legal basis by research organisations in Europe.

Legal Obligation

Legal obligation is the simplest and probably safest legal basis a controller can rely on, because when a legal obligation is established, the relevant law should automatically provide for the exemption under Article 9(2) and include appropriate and specific safeguards. Currently, such obligations exist in the context of population health registries, where healthcare organizations, such as hospitals and clinics, are required to transfer specific types of patient data to designated health registries. A similar situation occurs in countries that establish national or regional genome centres, where genome-sequencing organizations are legally required to submit genomic and related health data from their patients.

However, the legal basis for disclosing data to potential data users in these cases is not Article 6(1)(c). This is because data disclosure follows a defined data governance framework, which requires the health registry or repository to make a considered decision about whether to disclose the data. Therefore, a legal obligation is not an appropriate basis for contributing data to individual research

projects. The same applies to data users themselves. There is no legal obligation requiring a data user to conduct a specific research study. While the organization may be legally tasked with certain broad research areas, the data user has significant discretion in defining the research questions. Additionally, the processing of personal data for healthcare provision is assigned as a task rather than as a legal obligation, since it is not possible to pre-determine the processing with required level of specificity.

However, in the EHDS, the “Health Data Holders” act under a legal obligation combined with a suitable exemption under Article 9(2) GDPR) where they process personal electronic health data for the characterisation of the data and when they disclose relevant datasets to the “Health Data Access Bodies” following the issuance of a data permit.

A Task Carried Out in the Public Interest

Scientific research is frequently conducted by public or publicly funded organizations and serves the public interest. As a result, these entities, due to their public nature, could reasonably rely on the widely recognized legal basis for public authorities under the first part of Art. 6(1)(e), which allows data processing "for the performance of a task carried out in the public interest," instead of seeking consent.⁸² However, the basis of the processing must be laid down in either Union or Member State law to which the controller is subject (Arts. 6(1)(e), 6(3), and 9(2)(j) GDPR). In this case a task rather than a purpose is prescribed by the law, which means there is discretion as to the purposes that are covered by the law. The task is often part of the mission given to an entity by a Union or Member State law. Again, the EHDS Regulation is intended to address and widen the possibility to exploit this legal basis to address the fact that not all Member States have implemented national laws that would enable controllers from these countries to rely on GDPR Arts. 6(1)(e) and 9(2)(j). Public interest is far less cumbersome and potentially further reduces the burden associated with consent and, also, controller using this legal basis can benefit from derogations from data subjects' rights obligations.

The sharing and reuse of data in scientific research, particularly by public research institutions, is often viewed as research support rather than research itself and making data available to other researchers or repositories doesn't always align with their legal research mission. Some organizations, like health registries or biobanks, are legally authorized to share data with external researchers. In some EU countries, laws enable the creation of data sharing infrastructures to facilitate research by managing health data. These DSIs operate under specific legal frameworks, allowing them to share data for research purposes. However, legal and governance issues arise when trying to share data through pan-European DSIs, which aim to harmonize cross-border data access. These challenges stem from different national laws and data governance policies, which can hinder broader collaboration.

For public sector data users, Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR provides a legal basis for processing data in the public interest, but this typically applies to public research institutions, not private entities. When

⁸² Roxanne Meilak Borg and Mireille Martine Caruana, ‘Alternative Legal Bases for Processing Health Data for Scientific Research Purposes’ (2024) 18 Masaryk University Journal of Law and Technology

an organization's mission includes conducting research, its researchers can rely on a legal basis related to performing a task in the public interest. However, other types of entities, such as commercial companies, typically do not have this legal mandate in most countries, meaning they cannot rely on the Article 6(1)(e) legal basis. One exception is Finland, where scientific research can generally be pursued under Article 6(1)(e) regardless of the type of organization. However, this broad application of the research mission does not extend to the processing of special categories of data, like health or genetic data. To process such data, a separate exemption under Article 9(2) must be established, in addition to the legal basis under Article 6(1). While most EU Member States have implemented the scientific research exemption under Article 9(2)(j) in their national laws, many still require research ethics consent where feasible, and this requirement can only be waived with explicit approval from a competent ethics committee.⁸³

While many EU Member States allow exemptions for scientific research, some still require consent, particularly in Southern and Eastern Europe. In healthcare, professionals can process data for patient care under Article 6(1)(e) or 6(1)(b) (performance of a contract), but legal ambiguities exist when they need to use data from patients not under their direct care. Some countries have addressed this by allowing such data sharing explicitly in healthcare processes.

Legitimate Interest

If a controller cannot rely on a law to process personal data for scientific research purposes under Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR, they may consider using legitimate interest (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR) as an alternative legal basis. However, this legal basis is not available to public authorities in the execution of their tasks. Similar to 'task' under Article 6(1)(e), an interest is broader than a purpose, and many purposes can be pursued under an interest. The interest must be real and present, corresponding to current activities or a benefit expected in the immediate future; interests that are too speculative will not be sufficient. To use the legal basis under Article 6(1)(f) GDPR, the controller must first identify a legitimate interest that necessitates the processing. Then, the controller must balance this legitimate interest against the data subject's interests, fundamental rights, and freedoms, considering factors such as the data subject's reasonable expectations (as outlined in Recital 47 GDPR) to assess and test if its own interest does not unduly impact on the interests and fundamental rights of the data subject.

When relying on legitimate interest, there is also a requirement of an appropriate exemption under Article 9(2) to overcome the general prohibition on processing health and genetic data. While processing personal data under Article 6(1)(f) GDPR does not require the controller to rely on external laws beyond the GDPR, this is not the case for Article 9(2) exemptions when dealing with special categories of personal data. Therefore, to rely on a relevant Article 9(2) exemption, such as Article 9(2)(j), in conjunction with Article 6(1)(f), the controller must be authorized to process special

⁸³ Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Edward S Dove, Legal bases for effective secondary use of health and genetic data in the EU: time for new legislative solutions to better harmonize data for cross-border sharing?, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2024;, ipae014, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae014>

categories of data under Member State or Union law. This law must allow for the secondary use of special categories of personal data in the relevant fields. Many Member States lift the prohibition on such processing for research purposes, which may include making data available for future research use.

In healthcare, the implementation of Article 9(2)(h) into the relevant laws is largely limited to the context of medical professionals' interactions with their own patients. Therefore, in many scenarios involving the reuse of health and genetic data in the healthcare context, the Article 9(2)(h) exemption will not be valid. However, this situation may change with the application of the EHDS.⁸⁴

Lawfulness of Processing Genomic Data for Communication of Incidental Findings

Genomic data sets have become essential drivers of genetic and genomic research. However, it remains unclear what responsibilities should be assumed in handling incidental findings and individual research results that may have potential health, reproductive, or personal significance for the contributors.⁸⁵ The analysis of genomic sequence data can uncover clinically relevant information about individuals and their relatives who have submitted their data for scientific research. During secondary use, the user may identify information related to diseases or predispositions in an individual that was not part of the original research purpose and may be unknown to the individual. These discoveries are referred to as incidental findings (IF). The core ethical questions are: what information, if any, IFs should be shared with individuals whose genetic data and samples are stored in biobanks or archived datasets? Who should be responsible for providing these genetic/genomic research results to the individuals? Additionally, what policies should be established to regulate these practices?

The uncertainties surrounding IF are greater still in secondary use contexts compared to primary contexts. Secondary use contexts may be very distant from a patient care context. Secondary use may occur many years after sequencing. The health and familial situations of a data subject are not fully known to the data user and become more uncertain with time. Another difficulty in cross-border secondary use contexts is that reporting IF requires dedicated coordination and collaboration between data users. Therefore, regarding the need to communicate incidental findings, it is recommended to create a policy for IF that mandates data users to return IF to the data subject via data holding institution. Therefore, it excludes any direct interaction between the researcher and the data subject. Decisions about how to report findings should be made according to the local IF policy, ensuring respect for local legal, ethical, clinical, and feasibility considerations.

⁸⁴ Regina Becker, Davit Chokoshvili, Edward S Dove, Legal bases for effective secondary use of health and genetic data in the EU: time for new legislative solutions to better harmonize data for cross-border sharing?, *International Data Privacy Law*, 2024;, ipae014, <https://doi.org/10.1093/idpl/ipae014>

⁸⁵ Wolf SM, Crock BN, Van Ness B, et al. Managing incidental findings and research results in genomic research involving biobanks and archived data sets. *Genet Med*. 2012;14(4):361-384. doi:10.1038/gim.2012.23

Communicating genomic incidental findings is a processing activity that needs both a legal basis for processing personal data⁸⁶ and exemption from the general prohibition on the processing of health and genetic data.⁸⁷ From the ethical and legal standpoint, the only plausible legal basis is consent, which respects the autonomy of data subjects to opt in or out. The laboratory can either (i) seek and report incidental findings included on the list to the ordering clinician or (ii) not seek or report such findings. Option (i) runs the risk of imposing knowledge on the parents, child, and future young adult that they might nonetheless prefer not to have received but offers potential medical benefit both to the child and at-risk family members. In contrast, option (ii) withholds information that is potentially lifesaving for the child, one of the parents, and potentially other family members—information they would otherwise have no reason to suspect.⁸⁸

From the legal perspective, the situation is more complex for the options that primary collection of genomic data is built on legislation rather than consent, meaning there are specific obligations and requirements applicable to the user (researcher) at the EU or national level. These options are provided in letters (g), substantial public interest, (i), public health, (h), healthcare, as well as (j) statistics, historical and scientific research.

The relevant exemptions are consent, vital interest, and data made manifestly public.

Consent

Consent must be provided in a clear and affirmative manner that is freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous (Article 4(11) GDPR). For consent to be valid, as clarified by Article 7 and Recital 42, the controller must be able to demonstrate that the data subject has agreed to the processing. Recital 42 also specifies that informed consent requires the data subject to be aware of at least the controller's identity and the purpose of processing.

Thus, consent can serve as a legal basis for processing health data to communicate incidental findings, but only in certain circumstances—such as when the entity making the findings originally obtained the data through consent or if the data were acquired from the subject under a different legal basis and consent can be collected at that time. When written consent is obtained, the controller has sufficient proof to justify consent as the legal basis for returning incidental findings. Such consent can easily meet the requirement for specificity as it pertains solely to the transmission of incidental findings in line with the established policy. If the controller provides enough information about the processing and its consequences, this consent is considered informed, freely given, and unambiguous.

However, this scenario typically applies to primary data use. In cases of secondary use of data through other sources, where no direct contact with the data subjects is anticipated, consent is impractical for

⁸⁶ Article 6(1) of the GDPR

⁸⁷ Article 9(2) of the GDPR

⁸⁸ ACMG, *Genet. Med.* (2013); www.acmg.net/docs/Incidental_Findings_in_Clinical_Genomics_A_Clarification.pdf.

downstream users. At the time consent is sought for returning IF, the user (as the controller) is not yet identified, which means the conditions for valid consent outlined in Recital 42 cannot be fully met.

Consent is the most suitable legal basis in situations where data subjects explicitly agree that clinically relevant incidental findings should be communicated by the users to relevant entities on the national level. Consent can be seen as sufficiently informed because the actual identity of the controller will not influence the decision on the return of incidental findings and will not change in any way the risks to or even risk perception of the data subjects.

Vital Interest

The GDPR allows the processing of personal data based on vital interests, though under strict limitations, especially concerning sensitive data. The use of Article 9(2)(c) in healthcare without relying on Article 9(2)(h) GDPR is highly restricted. Article 9(2)(c) requires that processing be necessary to protect the data subject's vital interests and can only be invoked when the data subject is physically or legally incapable of giving consent. Recital 46 interprets "vital" to mean essential to the life of the data subject, and Recital 112 extends this to include physical integrity. Recital 46 further advises that the vital interest basis should only be used as a last resort when no other lawful reason for processing is available.

While reportable incidental findings are health-related (only clinically actionable findings are returned), they do not typically involve life-or-death situations. Hence, data subjects are usually given the option to be informed. However, the "physical integrity" of the person might be affected if their health could be influenced by receiving or not receiving such findings. The exception could apply when processing sensitive data is necessary for medical treatment, whether lifesaving or for serious but non-life-threatening conditions (e.g., a broken limb), or during humanitarian emergencies.

To invoke vital interests for communicating incidental findings, the processing must protect vital interests, and the data subject must be physically or legally incapable of giving consent. This second condition is more challenging to meet. Physically incapable may refer to situations where the individual is unable to communicate, such as being unconscious or paralysed. Legal incapability, though not explicitly defined, likely refers to the legal capacity to consent. The European Data Protection Board notes that legal incapability may involve situations such as a person being unconscious and in need of urgent medical care. Although there is no case law on "legally incapable" under the GDPR, related EU legislation suggests this refers to legal incapacity, not legal impossibility, as might arise in secondary use scenarios like incidental findings in downstream processing.

We would also assume that, in life-or-death situations where obtaining consent is impossible for any reason, the vital interest of the data subject would be sufficient grounds to proceed. However, for less critical information, it is likely that a balancing exercise would be necessary to determine whether a vital interest can indeed be claimed. If obtaining consent is not impossible, meaning there are alternative options to obtain a permission for the processing, vital interest is not a suitable choice.

Manifestly Made Public

Whether Article 9(2)(e) applies depends on the interpretation of "manifestly made public" and whether genomic data in a repository qualifies as public. The GDPR does not define what constitutes data being "manifestly made public," and the EDPB has not provided specific guidance. However, the UK Information Commissioner's Office (ICO) states that for data to be manifestly made public, it must be genuinely accessible to the general public, not just theoretically available (e.g., in a specialised library or mentioned in court). Disclosures to a limited audience do not necessarily meet this criterion. This view is supported by the European Court of Justice in case C-252/21, which states that manifestly public data must be accessible to the general public, and the data subject must have clearly chosen to make it available to an unlimited audience. In the case of controlled-access repositories, this condition is not met. Even if the data were obtained with consent, subsequent access is limited to qualified users for specific purposes rather than being available to the general public.

Conclusions

In this document we have presented a holistic overview of the European legal, governance, and policy framework regulating secondary use of genomic data with a special focus on GDPR and analysed appropriate legal bases for the genomic data sharing for the purpose of scientific research, policy making and clinical use (legal basis for disclosing incidental findings) to ensure key legal and ethical requirements are respected in cancer genomics. There is a large number of stakeholders and corresponding human power (clinicians, scientists, wetlabs, data scientists, data stewards, software developers, sysadmins, legal support, policy makers, managers etc.) involved in high-quality data sharing (especially genomics and/or health data) which requires at least a basic knowledge of the genomic data sharing legal landscape to reach a common understanding. Understanding the nature of genomic data sharing barriers is crucial for the Can.Heal consortium in achieving its objectives in a compliant manner.

Even though GDPR provides a basic legal framework for data sharing, it does not provide simple solution for (cross-border) genomic data reuse for clinical and scientific purposes. However, it foresees existence and encourages creation of another legislative framework in this field. Additional legislative measures are needed to ensure a valid legal basis under GDPR for data controllers involved in genomic data reuse, especially given the challenges with obtaining valid consent. While legislation can occur at both the national and EU levels, the EU-level legislation is more practical. National interpretations of GDPR have already diverged significantly, making harmonized implementation unlikely. Therefore, the best path forward to ensure valid legal bases for cross-border health data reuse is through EU legislation. In this respect, it is necessary to be primarily well-versed in the GDPR, which provides for data processing terminology and explains possibilities for data sharing (mostly) on national level, but be also mindful of emerging data-driven legislation focused on a cross-border data transfer and data reuse like DGA or EHDS bearing in mind cyber security requirements.

From the perspective of existing European data-sharing initiatives the proposed EHDS Regulation is both promising and concerning. On the one hand, if implemented, the EHDS Regulation could address many of the key legal obstacles to data sharing and reuse that arise from shortcomings in the current legal framework. On the other hand, the benefits of the EHDS Regulation are limited to the European health ecosystem it aims to regulate—that is, the EHDS itself. External platforms or repositories that are not part of the EHDS ecosystem would not enjoy the advantages of this favourable legal regime. In fact, such external entities could be disadvantaged by the EHDS's success, as the Regulation introduces new legal entities and technical infrastructures with overlapping functions. As a result, entities engaged in health data-sharing activities outside the EHDS framework risk being overshadowed by the infrastructures and actors established within it. This underscores the need to closely monitor the development of the EHDS Regulation.

The analysis of the lawfulness of certain processing activities in the third chapter along with theoretical explanation of the necessary notions in the first and second chapter showed how essential legal bases, and the purpose of the processing are for the data governance. The interrelatedness

between GDPR and EHDS is even more visible knowing EHDS creates additional legal bases for secondary use of genomic data and “Health Data Holders”, “Health Data Access Bodies” and “Health Data Users” introduced there are controllers and processors according to the GDPR.

As mentioned many times earlier, every processing activity needs to have a legal basis, and the complex genomic data processing chain contains many processing activities. In the world of data reuse, it is vitally important to make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). Data cleaning, standardising and harmonising for the reuse is therefore essential to achieve this task. Sadly, at present, there is no legal basis for such activity provided in the EHDS. On the side of the Health Data User, after creation of possible enriched or curated dataset there is no valid legal basis to have the resultant dataset preserved for own or other parties’ future uses. The EHDS also fell short of creating a unified mechanism for accessing electronic health data for secondary use across the EU (as stated in recital 37 of the EHDS). Additionally, it reinstates the option for Member States to apply their own regulations regarding the processing of genetic and genomic data.

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